

The map displays the railbelt of Alaska, highlighted in red, connecting major hubs like Anchorage, Fairbanks, and Seward. It also shows various power plants (hydro and fuel) and transmission lines (under construction and proposed). Key geographical features like the Chugach Mountains and Wrangell Mountains are labeled. A legend at the bottom explains the symbols used for power plants, substations, and transmission lines. A scale bar indicates distances up to 50 miles.

Electrifying Alaska's Railbelt: A Generation and Transmission History, 1904-2024

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Glossary

AEA—Alaska Energy Authority
AEC—Alaska Engineering Commission
AEG&T—Alaska Electric Generation and Transmission Cooperative
AIA—Alaska Intertie Agreement
AIDEA—Alaska Industrial Development and Export Authority
AL&P—Anchorage Light & Power
APA—Alaska Power Authority (State of Alaska, precursor to AEA)
AREA—Alaska Railbelt Energy Authority
ASCC—Alaska Systems Coordinating Council
BCF—Billion cubic feet
BPMC—Bradley Project Management Committee
CAPA—Central Alaska Power Association
CEA—Chugach Electric Association
CVEA—Copper Valley Electric Association
DOE—U.S. Department of Energy
ERCOT—Electric Reliability Council of Texas
ERO—Electric Reliability Organization
FERC—Federal Energy Regulatory Commission
FMUS—Fairbanks Municipal Utility System
G&T—Generation and Transmission
GVEA—Golden Valley Electric Association
GW—Gigawatt
HEA—Homer Electric Association
HVDC—High-voltage direct current
IIJA—Infrastructure, Investment, and Jobs Act
IOC—Intertie Operating Committee
IRA—Inflation Reduction Act
ISER—Institute for Social and Economic Research
ISO—Independent System Operator
kV—Kilovolt
kW—Kilowatt
kWh—Kilowatt-hour
MEA—Matanuska Electric Association
ML&P—Anchorage Municipal Light and Power
MW—Megawatt
NERC—North American Electric Reliability Corporation
RCA—Regulatory Commission of Alaska
REA—Rural Electrification Administration
REGA—Railbelt Electric Grid Authority
RIPR—Alaska Railbelt Integrated Resource Plan
RTO—Railbelt Transmission Organization
TAPS—Trans-Alaska Pipeline System
USACE—U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
USO—Unified System Operator

Introduction

The year 1904 heralded a bright future for the electrification of Alaska. In two distant cities, nearly 500 rail miles from each other, Alaskans were busy electrifying the far north. In the bustling town of Seward—founded as the terminus of the Alaska Central Railroad—Seward Light and Power began constructing a 225 kW hydroelectric generator on Lowell Creek that would power the frontier community by 1905. A postcard sold at the time boasted that Seward “has 1,000 population, electric light plant, telephone exchange, public school, daily newspaper...and is growing rapidly.”¹ At the other end of the eventual 470-mile rail line, the Northern Commercial Company had constructed a biomass-fired steam plant that burned an astounding 8,500 cords of wood per year to provide Fairbanks with heat and electricity. The “steam-heated pioneers” of Fairbanks created a permanent settlement in Interior Alaska that would become the northern star of the Railbelt. This power plant helped to cement Fairbanks as the regional center of Interior Alaska and the future terminus of the Alaska Railroad.²

These two seemingly distant and disparate electric developments—largely forgotten in Alaska today—were catalyzed by the discovery of gold and formed the northern and southern termini of what would become Alaska’s most important electrical infrastructure: the Railbelt electric grid.³ While the original Central Alaska Railroad ended in bankruptcy, Congressional legislation in 1914 began the construction of the “government railroad” that eventually linked Seward to Fairbanks and created the new railroad town of Anchorage. These developments sparked a new chapter of electrical transmission, with the first major radial lines constructed near Fairbanks and Anchorage in the 1920s. By the 1930s, coal and diesel plants replaced these early biomass and hydro plants in Fairbanks and Seward and marked a significant shift to a fossil energy system. The dream of a unified Railbelt grid was only realized in the 1960s and 1980s, when “hydro lines” connected hydropower facilities on the Kenai Peninsula to Anchorage and Fairbanks.

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Figure 1: “First completed mile of the Alaska Central Railway and headquarters building, Seward, Alaska, June 1904.” John E. Ballaine Photograph Collection. PH Coll 1185, University of Washington Libraries, Special Collections, AWC1153.

¹ “Looking across the town of Seward, Alaska, showing Alaska Central Railway and port, between 1901 and 1911,” John E. Ballaine Photograph Collection. PH Coll 1185, University of Washington Libraries, Special Collections.

² Tom Alton, *Alaska in the Progressive Age: A Political History* (Fairbanks: University of Alaska Press, 2019).

³ While Seward and Fairbanks marked the original beginning and end of the railroad, the line grew over time and the electric grid sprawled significantly beyond the narrow confines of the railroad.

This paper analyzes the historic buildout of electrical generation and transmission on the Railbelt grid—the single largest machine in America’s largest state. At the highest level, it asks: how did the Railbelt electrify and become a grid? How did Alaska’s Railbelt develop generation and transmission (G&T) infrastructure? What were the crucial events and historical eras that most influenced this growth and development? Furthermore, it seeks to understand *why* and *how* various Alaskan entities along the Railbelt—from small private utilities to electrical cooperatives, the U.S. Military, and the Alaska Energy Authority (AEA)—constructed critical energy infrastructure. This research is not simply concerned with history; it also seeks to understand the pace of Railbelt infrastructure development as a baseline to compare against future generation and transmission investments required for decarbonization. While interested in the *why*, *how*, and *where* of development, this study does not analyze demand-side and consumption dynamics.

Findings and Arguments

This paper offers six findings concerning the development of electrical generation and transmission throughout Alaska’s Railbelt.

First, Railbelt G&T development grew organically with the wider economy and “in a randomly responsive manner.”⁴ Electrification radiated outward from small cities in the early 20th century to regional microgrids in the postwar era. The interconnected Railbelt transmission system was primarily stitched together in the 1960s and 1980s from this constellation of independent electrical systems. The grid first grew regionally and then became interconnected between regions, providing low-cost hydro, economy power, and redundancy.⁵ While early electric systems were founded as either private or federal systems, in time, rural electric cooperatives became the regional utilities, acquiring municipal, private, and federal systems. This process of historical consolidation continues today, with four dominant electric cooperatives supplying power to the Railbelt.⁶ Coordination between Railbelt cooperatives, the federal government, and the State of Alaska—all forms of public power—has driven the electrification of the Railbelt region.

⁴ U.S. Department of the Interior, *Alaska Power Survey, 1969* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1969).

⁵ The use of the term “interconnected” here and afterwards is meant in a technical manner—the synchronous operation of a linked system, where all pieces of alternating current equipment operate at the same frequency.

⁶ As of this publication, the municipality of Seward is actively trying to sell its assets.

Figure 2: Railbelt historic generation capacity, 1904–2024. Visualization by Gus Lewis

Second, the Railbelt witnessed several key periods of remarkable generation and transmission growth. These “golden eras,” as one could call them, occurred when cooperative, state, and federal incentives aligned. Since 1904, the Railbelt has constructed over 2.7 gigawatts (GW) of electrical generation and over 1,600 miles of high-voltage transmission. Each period has built from the accomplishments and infrastructures of the preceding era, resulting in an accretionary development pattern.

1916–1929	AK Railroad and coal access, FE Co. and Eklutna, first transmission
1952–1962	5 DoD CHPP plants, Eklutna and Kenai hydro, Kenai-ANC 115 kV
1975–1984	Pipeline Boom: 784 MW oil and fossil gas generation buildout
1985–1991	“Bradley Belt”: Alaska Intertie and Bradley Lake hydropower
2012–2016	660 MW: Fossil and landfill gas, utility-scale wind, Healy 2 restart

Figure 3: Golden eras of Railbelt generation and transmission buildout.

In the 1920s, the building of the “Government Railroad” spurred power development—especially coal-fired steam plants—along the Railbelt and precipitated the region’s first transmission systems in Anchorage (Eklutna Hydro) and Fairbanks (FE Company). In the decade between 1952 and 1962, a period of defense electrification witnessed five large DoD coal plants, the 30 MW Eklutna hydro project, a nuclear reactor at Ft. Greely, federal plans for a Railbelt transmission system and power pool, and the rise of Railbelt cooperatives, which constructed the first interregional transmission systems to tap hydropower on the Kenai Peninsula. The period of 1975–1984 constituted the single largest total generation buildout in Alaska’s history, with 784 MW constructed amidst the pipeline boom—an average of 78 MW per year. The construction of the Alaska Intertie and Bradley Lake hydroelectric

plants between 1985 and 1991 did not add a historic level of generation capacity but finally linked Anchorage and Fairbanks and provided the Railbelt’s most important source of low-cost electricity. Finally, 2012–2016 witnessed 660 MW of new generation—an unprecedented average of 132 MW per year—as Railbelt cooperatives ended a 30-year wholesale generation agreement and replaced aging generation (mostly placed on standby) with a fossil gas buildout.⁷ These years also saw two major wind farms on the Railbelt, as well as a landfill methane gas project—signaling the beginning of a utility-scale buildout of renewable generation on the Railbelt.

Despite the long-running Alaskan perception of federal neglect, a crucial factor in these moments of buildout was the support from the federal government, especially for generation.⁸ The federal government, via the Alaska Engineering Commission, Department of Defense, and Bureau of Reclamation, constructed over 250 MW of generation. In the 1940s and 1950s, federally owned power facilities constituted the majority of Railbelt generation capacity and remained as high as a third of nameplate capacity until the early 1970s. The influence of the federal government is not surprising during the Territorial era, but its continued involvement in Alaska’s energy affairs well into statehood remains remarkable from a national perspective.⁹

Third, while hydroelectric only contributed ~20% of the Railbelt electricity production in 2023, historically, it has been the prime mover in constructing interregional transmission infrastructure.¹⁰ While Railbelt is an appropriate name for Alaska’s biggest grid, most of its major interregional connections were forged with the construction of “hydro lines.”¹¹ When bulk power was first moved between cooperatives on the Railbelt grid (in 1953 from Chugach Electric to Matanuska Electric), the power flowed via the original 33 kV Eklutna hydroelectric lines constructed in 1929 and 1942. The Bureau of Reclamation constructed the first modern high-voltage transmission of the Railbelt (115 kV), connecting Anchorage and Palmer, as part of the 30 MW Eklutna hydroelectric plant in 1955. When CEA connected Seward and Homer to the Anchorage grid system, it did so primarily to move power from the new 16 MW Cooper Lake hydroelectric plant constructed in 1960.¹² The Willow–Healy Intertie was designed to move power from the never-built Susitna hydroelectric project and ultimately served as the crucial line to move power from the 120 MW Bradley Lake project to Fairbanks. With the completion of the Alaska Intertie in 1985, the Railbelt became a singular “grid” as defined by the Federal Power Act,

⁷ This 660 MW capacity does not include the 50 MW from the Healy 2 reboot, which could be considered a new generation source since it did not operate commercially in 1999 and had significant capital costs to restart.

⁸ The “neglect thesis” has a long history in Alaskan politics, see Terrance Cole, “The History of a History: The Making of Jeanette Paddock Nichol’s Alaska,” *Pacific Northwest Quarterly* 77 (October 1986): 130–138.

⁹ For a discussion of state vs. federal energy development, see Christopher F. Jones, *Routes of Power: Energy and Modern America* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2014), 11.

¹⁰ Alaska has primarily relied on generation proximate to natural resources and the superior economics of transmitting energy by wire to distant load centers. This dynamic applies not only to hydropower but also to Healy coal and Beluga gas.

¹¹ The term “hydro lines” is widely used in Canada, where long distance transmission lines are synonymous with carrying hydroelectric power. For example, see Riley Sparks, “New research at Hydro-Quebec aims to take advantage of energy ‘revolution,’” *The Globe and Mail*, February 1, 2017, <https://www.nationalobserver.com/2017/02/01/news/new-research-hydro-quebec-aims-take-advantage-energy-revolution>, accessed November 20, 2023.

¹² The Cooper Lake facility was later upgraded to 20 MW.

albeit a weakly connected one.¹³ While this is not a comparative study, it's worth noting the smaller hydroelectric facilities have served as the basis for connecting interregional grids in numerous other northern polities, notably Iceland and Norway.¹⁴ The influence of hydroelectricity on the system is such that one could easily refer to the Railbelt system as the “Bradley Belt and its hydro lines.”

Fourth, throughout the majority of the Railbelt's history, there has been an asymmetry between investment in generation versus transmission. Utilities have focused far more on building local and regional generation. This is partially because of their histories as independent entities that had to be able to self-generate and could not rely on backup from a distant utility. No single unified operator was concerned about the *entire grid* until the 21st Century. Furthermore, many utilities on the Railbelt provided not only electrical generation but also steam heat via combined heat and power plants. These were “must run” facilities. To the extent that utilities constructed longer-distance transmission, it was exceptionally rare that this was stand-alone transmission disconnected from a particular generation. Partially due to this asymmetry, the Railbelt grid's interconnections tended to be “weak links” compared with the Lower 48 systems. With some exceptions, transmission systems in Alaska were generally not built to move bulk power between regions. Utilities constructed transmission systems for reserve sharing or providing power for plants that go down either for maintenance or unexpected disruption.¹⁵ Ultimately, Railbelt utilities spent far more time and money on local and regional generation than on interregional high-voltage transmission.

In many ways, the challenges of the Railbelt mirror the history of national electrical interconnection. In the Lower 48, engineers and politicians first envisioned a national grid in the 1910s, and by the 1930s, the development of large, interconnected networks emerged as the expected path for growth, according to power systems historian Thomas Hughes.¹⁶ Since the construction of the Alaska Railroad, building a Railbelt grid and interconnecting the region's major urban centers emerged as key goals of the Territory then State of Alaska. Yet, like the construction and operation of a national grid, actually realizing an interconnected power system demonstrated just how complex power networks are. During key periods like the post-World War II era, the United States constructed a historic amount of

¹³ The Federal Power Act defines the grid as “facilities and control systems necessary for operating an interconnected electric energy transmission network (or any portion thereof); and electric energy from generation facilities needed to maintain transmission system reliability.” Federal Power Act, 16 U.S.C. §791a et seq. (1935), https://www.ferc.gov/sites/default/files/2021-04/federal_power_act.pdf.

¹⁴ For the example of Iceland, see David Roberts interviewing Halla Logadottir, “What's the Deal with Iceland,” *Volts Podcast*, October 18, 2023; Gwen Holdmann and Erlingur Gudleifsson, “Lessons Learned from Iceland's Ring Grid: Ownership and Asset Management Strategies for an Islanded Grid,” ACEP White Paper, 2023.

¹⁵ Brian Hickey, “Upgrading the Railbelt Grid for Efficiency and Reliability,” *Alaska Powerline Podcast*, April 6, 2023, <https://open.spotify.com/episode/57EaoQzyOdjltqE6FquXc3>. This is not a problem unique to the Railbelt. Indeed, in the 2020s, more than 90% of transmission spending is focused on local lower-voltage lines that are not subject to regional planning processes. These projects address local needs for grid reliability or additional capacity but are disconnected from regional planning and power-sharing dynamics. Jeff St. John, “Lots of Demand, Too Little Grid: The State of the U.S. Power Sector,” *Canary Media*, January 2, 2025, <https://www.canarymedia.com/articles/transmission/lots-of-demand-too-little-grid-the-us-power-sector-in-2024>, accessed January 3, 2025.

¹⁶ Thomas P. Hughes, *Networks of Power: Electrification in Western Society, 1880–1930* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1983). For the claim about an envisioned national grid, see Julie Coen, “When the Grid was a Grid,” *IEEE* (January 2019).

transmission but then struggled to successfully operate a giant interconnected system. According to the U.S. Energy Information Agency, the nation quadrupled the amount of delivered electricity between 1950–1970.¹⁷ However, as electricity historian Julie Coen notes, a unified East–West national grid only functioned for less than a decade before becoming balkanized. In many ways, the Railbelt followed this national pattern.¹⁸

Fifth, the dream of an interconnected electron superhighway—the Railbelt grid—has existed as long as the railroad itself, but transmission and power pooling proved the hardest barriers to overcome. Transmission has remained particularly vexing for several reasons: the long history of the cooperative’s independence and need for self-reliance, the lack of a centralized transmission authority, and the daunting economics of creating a 230 kV and redundant “backbone” transmission grid. These challenges have been compounded by mixed incentives and policies from the state government. At times, the state has been flush with money for hydropower and transmission, with policies that spurred an interconnection building spree between 1985 and 2002; at other times, the state has been cash-poor and offered little support for transmission. State spending on transmission has created temporary subsidies to ratepayers but poses long-term problems with aging infrastructure and the need to fund transmission replacements and upgrades. Ultimately, while the state provided invaluable financial support for Bradley Lake and the Alaska Intertie, it did not empower a state energy office with strategic focus, long-term expertise, and appropriate authority to realize the energy projects outlined in countless state-sponsored studies.

Building and operating transmission in Alaska also faced challenges not commonly found in the Lower 48. Transmission lines often had to pass along the edges of glaciated mountains, through rockslide and avalanche zones, under iceberg-choaked rivers, and in conditions of high winds, icing, and snowfall. In Alaska, transmission remained more difficult to realize than in the Lower 48. Furthermore, because the Railbelt has always been disconnected from other interstate power systems, Alaska’s Railbelt grid has never fallen under the jurisdiction of the Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC). Without mandates from the FERC, Railbelt utilities have struggled to establish reliability standards, create a unified or independent grid operator, and cooperate on a range of issues. This failure of coordination on transmission and power pooling is not without trying: Railbelt history is replete with attempts to form G&T cooperatives or grid operators. The number of attempted “paper utilities” and “paper interties” that never came to fruition likely outnumbers existing utilities and interties.¹⁹

Sixth, the Railbelt’s generation mix has been in constant flux and evolution over the past 12 decades, and the flexibility of transmission has facilitated the diversification of generation. In the early years (1900–1960), biomass, hydroelectric, and coal generation dominated the Railbelt. With the discovery of methane gas in Cook Inlet and the phenomenal postwar growth of Anchorage, gas emerged as an

¹⁷ In 1950, 334 GWh were delivered. By 1960, 759 GWh were delivered, a 227% increase. By 1970, 1,535 GWh were delivered, a 202% increase since 1960. See EIA Table 7.2 Electricity Net Generation: Total (All Sectors), https://www.eia.gov/totalenergy/data/monthly/pdf/sec7_5.pdf, accessed August 2024.

¹⁸ Cohen, “When the Grid was a Grid.”

¹⁹ For examples of G&T cooperatives or transmission authorities, see Central Alaska Power Association (CAPA), Trans-Alaska Electric Cooperative, Alaska Electric Generation and Transmission Cooperative (AEG&T), Alaska Railbelt Energy Authority (AREA), Railbelt Electric Grid Authority (REGA), Alaska Railbelt Transmission and Electric Company (ARCTEC), and Alaska Railbelt Transco (ART).

inexpensive and dominant fuel source for the contemporary Railbelt (1960–present). Due to the centrality of Cook Inlet methane gas, concerns around supply have been an issue not only in the present or in 2010 but stretching as far back as the late 1970s. Oil generation has also played a surprisingly large role in the Railbelt since the 1970s, the moment when the rest of the nation largely purged oil from electricity generation.²⁰ Most recently, uncertainties about Cook Inlet supply, the need for better regulation, and increased attention to carbon emissions have focused development efforts on non-hydro renewable energy resources.²¹

Regardless of the specific generation mix at any historical moment, expanding transmission has facilitated a more diversified and resilient grid. While transmission was built to serve particular generators or loads, the nature of the infrastructure gives it a flexible character that enables it to evolve over time and carry new sources of power to new sources of load. Major long-distance transmission lines were primarily constructed as 115 kV and 138 kV “hydro lines” but ultimately transmitted large amounts of gas-fired power. GVEA constructed the Northern Intertie to move coal, gas, and hydropower, yet it carried wind power from Eva Creek a decade after construction. CEA’s Beluga lines have carried thousands of gigawatt hours of gas generation and may carry major wind, solar, or hydro generation in the near future. The existence of historic conduits facilitates new sources of generation. As historian Christopher Jones argues, “The *roots* of America’s energy transitions can be found in the building of *routes* along which coal, oil, and electricity were shipped.”²² The nature of generational buildout largely structured the initial growth in the transmission system, while subsequent transmission extensions were based on power sharing and new sources of load.

This paper examines these six arguments chrono-thematically between 1904 and 2024. **From Tidewater to Golden Heart, 1904–1938** witnessed the earliest electric systems, where towns and mines from Seward to Fairbanks used wood, coal, and hydropower for limited electrical development. The construction of the Alaska Railroad provided a formative template for growth and electrification. **War and Statehood, 1939–1961** saw the federal government and U.S. military construct major bases and hydroelectric facilities during World War II and the early Cold War. The creation of rural electric cooperatives supercharged the growth of Alaska’s electrical networks and enabled the first interregional connections (the Anchorage–Kenai system in 1961). **Gassing Up, 1962–1984** saw the Railbelt tap Cook Inlet methane gas and struggle to contain the growth of the pipeline boom. This golden age of growth saw five times more electrical capacity added per year than the postwar defense boom. Growth declined during the period of **Oil and Water, 1985–2002**, as the state invested oil dollars in hydroelectric projects. (The old saying goes that oil and water don’t mix, but in the Railbelt’s electrical history, they have). Struggling with aging generation and the need to better coordinate transmission, **Repowering the**

²⁰ Alaska and Hawaii are the two top states for petroleum-fired electricity generation. In 2021, 65.4% and 14.9% of Hawaii and Alaska’s electricity generation, respectively, came from petroleum. Nuclear Energy Institute, “State Electricity Generation Fuel Shares,” <https://www.nei.org/resources/statistics/state-electricity-generation-fuel-shares>, accessed December 13, 2024.

²¹ It is important to note that historically Alaskans have focused on renewable energy development for economic, not climate or carbon reasons. Following the oil crises of the 1970s, the State of Alaska invested considerable money in energy efficiency and renewable energy technologies. Perceptions of scarcity and economics, rather than environmental concerns, have driven historical energy decisions. The flip side of wanting to save Alaskan households money was the fact that state energy policy was being driven by a desire to disburse wealth from oil.

²² Jones, *Routes of Power*, 2.

Railbelt, 2003–2024 witnessed both a historic generation buildout (with wind and methane gas) and numerous attempts to create a grid authority.

I. From Tidewater to Golden Heart, 1904–1938

Alaska’s electrical history traces back to the 1890s, when a Juneau merchant named Willis Thorp installed a water wheel and an electrical generator on Gold Creek. A decade after Thomas Edison electrified lower Manhattan with the first commercial generating station at Pearl Street in 1882, Juneau became one of America’s early electrified cities.²³ Between the 1890s and 1920s, Juneau and southeastern Alaska remained the electric champions of the Territory. By 1908, southeastern Alaska had over 30 developed waterpower sites with a total capacity of roughly 11.5 MW.²⁴ Juneau’s major mines went “all electric” around 1910, with 23 kV transmission lines sending hydroelectric power from dams to load centers across the Gastineau Channel.²⁵

Contrary to the idea of a singular “gold rush,” Juneau was the first of dozens of gold rushes that brought waves of settlement and development to the far north.²⁶ The discovery of gold in the Klondike in 1896 brought tens of thousands of Euro-American settlers to Alaska and created the preconditions for today’s Railbelt grid—demand for energy and power. Prospectors and the residents of the communities that supported gold mining desired all the conveniences of modern technology they could afford and obtain. Communities like Seward, Nome, and Fairbanks were large and wealthy enough that commercial enterprises set up electrical generators. Wherever there was a sufficient concentration of people and capital, an electric generator soon buzzed to life.

Prior to the railroad, these early generating facilities had several defining characteristics. Communities installed local generators to meet local loads using locally available resources.²⁷ Generators were privately owned and operated as the dominant utilities in their respective cities. In terms of fuel sources, generators were often powered by local renewable sources—either biomass or hydropower. Following the development patterns of southeast Alaska, wherever possible, developers utilized hydroelectric resources due to their low operating costs.²⁸ These early facilities had limited distribution systems and no long-distance electrical transmission. The only long-distance electrical system of this era was the U.S. Army’s Washington-Alaska Military Cable and Telegraph System (WAMCATS), an innovative communication system that did not transmit electricity for power consumption. Finally, in the Railbelt

²³ Tim Bradner, “Hydro power in Southeast Intrigues Leaders,” *Alaska Journal of Commerce*, 2007.

²⁴ Eric P. Yould, “Alaska Plans Big Switch,” *IEEE Spectrum*, 1984.

²⁵ Treadwell Mine Historical Park. Juneau utilized these 23 kV transmission systems well into the 1970s. For a larger history of the subject, see Philip A. Wight, “A Brief History of Alaskan Electrification, 1893-2023,” in Peter Asmus, ed. *Alaska’s Energy Innovators: How Communities Are Responding to the Climate Crisis* (Fairbanks, AK: University of Alaska Press, 2025) (Forthcoming).

²⁶ There was a brief gold rush in Sitka following the American purchase of Alaska in 1867, but this was not a major event.

²⁷ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” March 27, 2015, 18.

²⁸ Despite its pioneering hydroelectric developments, for many years Juneau’s mines relied on coal and oil. “Energy Infrastructure—the Treadwell Transformer Room,” Treadwell Mine Historical Park. Juneau-Douglas City Museum & The Last Chance Mining Museum. Douglas, Alaska.

region, these power plants served limited residential and commercial electrical loads and did not provide power for larger-scale industrial customers, as was the case with mines in southeastern Alaska.

These early power resources proved unsustainable or problematic over the medium term. In Seward, avalanches and rockslides destroyed crucial generating components on Lowell Creek.²⁹ By the 1930s, Seward's mayor reported that the existing private hydroelectric service (Seward Light & Power Company) was unsatisfactory, charged high rates, offered limited capacity, and entirely failed at some point almost every winter. Congress moved for Seward to establish a municipal electrical utility and to construct a reliable power system.³⁰ Seward's new 300 kW diesel plant came online in 1938.³¹ In Fairbanks, the widespread clear-cutting of local wood resulted in a "timber famine" 15 years later that threatened the community's economic viability. To provide more consistent and economical power, Fairbanks turned to coal by the early 1920s with the arrival of the Alaska Railroad.

The question of transportation emerged as paramount from the very outset of the gold rushes. Both Fairbanks and Seward constructed early mining railroads before 1914, but these were never able to achieve interregional connections. While the federal government invested in early trail and road systems like the Trans-Alaska Military Trail (today known as the Richardson Highway), the problem of transportation was only resolved with the construction of a government railroad to the Interior.³² The decision by Congress and President Woodrow Wilson in 1915 to construct the Alaska Railroad would fundamentally transform the Territory and the electrification of Alaska. Ultimately, the transportation of electrons was closely linked to the transportation of humans and other commodities.

The decision to route the railroad between Seward and Fairbanks also created a new template for settlement and the booming technology of electricity in the 1920s. More than any other single infrastructure, the Alaska Railroad transformed the energy history of Alaska and created the essential template for the electrification of the region. This rail network, while not electrified, created a transportation pattern—the "Railbelt"—that became essential for future military and economic development. The Railbelt linked Alaska's biggest community in 1915, Fairbanks, with the established port of Seward and inspired a string of major settlements along its route, including Anchorage, Moose Pass, Palmer, Wasilla, Talkeetna, and Nenana. Quite simply, the route of the railroad presaged the route of Alaska's mass electrification.

²⁹ C.E. Ellsworth and R.W. Davenport, "A Water-Power Reconnaissance in South-Central Alaska," USGS Water Supply Paper 372, Government Printing Office, 1915.

³⁰ U.S. Senate, *Municipal Electric System for Seward, Alaska*, U.S. Senate Report 74-530, 74th Congress, 1st Session, April 18, 1936.

³¹ "Vote FOR Issuing Revenue Bonds for the City Electric System," *Seward Seaport Record*, August 30, 1949.

³² Alfred H. Brooks, *Blazing Alaska's Trails* (Fairbanks, AK: University of Alaska Press, 1973).

Figure 4: The Alaska Engineering Commission's 900 kW steam plant—the first coal power plant on the Railbelt—in the new railroad settlement of Anchorage in 1916. University of Washington Special Collections.

The electrical developments of this early railroad era had several notable features. Two principal parties—the AEC and private developers—constructed new electrical generation. Due to the railroad, coal-fired generation became widespread. To run railroad operations, generation plants were built in Anchorage, Curry, and Nenana. The AEC also owned coal mines in Eska and Chickaloon, each requiring generating plants.³³ These developments enabled the Railbelt to surpass Southeastern Alaska's installed capacity in the 1920s. Major hydroelectric and coal facilities emerged with railroad-driven growth in Anchorage and Fairbanks. Private developers constructed the first significant transmission systems to move this power beyond city limits. The end of this period witnessed the birth of an essential new public utility organization that would transform the Railbelt: the rural electric cooperative.

Energy was not an afterthought in the design and construction of the Alaska Railroad. Congress approved the line largely to “unlock” Interior Alaska and accelerate coal mining, which the Navy sought for its Pacific Fleet.³⁴ The railroad and its associated energy developments were always linked with national security. The railroad promoted a thriving coal market, which in turn powered electrification. Furthermore, federal planners aimed to open the Territory's timber resources for export and to promote agricultural development.³⁵ These energetic developments—coal, timber, and agriculture—structured both the route of the railroad and patterns of Alaskan development. Despite the long-term importance of the railroad, its completion in 1923 did not supercharge growth; Juneau and Ketchikan remained the largest cities as late as 1940.³⁶

³³ Theodore Chapin, “Mining Developments in the Matanuska Coal Field,” in *Mineral Resources of Alaska: Report on Progress of Investigations in 1918*, U.S. Geological Survey Bulletin 712 (Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 1920), 131–132.

³⁴ One historian devoted an entire chapter to coal in his history of the AKRR. See William H. Wilson, *Railroad in the Clouds: The Alaska Railroad in the Age of Steam, 1914-1945* (Boulder, CO: Pruett Publishing Co., 1977).

³⁵ William H. Wilson, “Developing Central Alaska's Forest Resources: The Alaska Railroad, 1923-1941,” *Journal of Forest History* (January 1981).

³⁶ Eric Sandberg, “A History of Alaskan Population Settlement” (Alaska Department of Labor and Workforce Development, April 2013), 11.

The railroad managed all services for the townsite, including electricity. The opening of the AEC's first coal 900 kW coal-fired steam plant in Anchorage in 1916 signaled the coming of the coal age for the Railbelt.

The railroad had a fraught relationship with energy. On the one hand, it needed coal and electricity to fuel its locomotives, power its buildings, and provide services for its employees. On the other hand, the railroad came under withering criticism of its Anchorage power plant from political critics (namely Nebraska Senator Robert B. Howell) opposed to public ownership of the railroad.³⁷ The AEC did not want to be the only provider of energy for Alaska's growing communities and was happy to support other electrification projects. Consequently, the Alaska Railroad met its own needs and eventually reduced its footprint in energy production and consumption.

Political criticism of the AEC's steam plant, combined with a fire that severely damaged the facility, prompted the Alaska Railroad to survey alternative energy sources in the region, namely a potential hydroelectric facility at Eklutna Lake. While the AEC quickly abandoned the project due to cost and time concerns, local businessman Frank Reed—a veteran of hydraulic mining and electric dredges in Nome—established the Anchorage Light and Power Company (AL&P) to privately construct the Eklutna project.³⁸ Between 1922 and 1929, Reed and his company studied, designed, and constructed a 2 MW hydroelectric facility at Eklutna Lake.

While Westinghouse and Tesla completed the first long-distance alternating current line from

Figure 5: Map for the Alaska railroad brochure, late 1940s or early 1950s. Note the prominence of coal fields and associated rail spurs. Source: The Alaska Railroad.

³⁷ Carberry and Lane, *Patterns of the Past: An Inventory of Anchorage's Historic Resources*, 107, found in Kristy Hollinger, "Early Electrification of Anchorage" (Ft. Collins, CO: Center for Environmental Management of Military Lands, 2002), 15–42.

³⁸ For the connection between mining and hydroelectric development, see Katherine Blunt, *California Burning: The Fall of Pacific Gas and Electric and What it Means for America's Power Grid* (New York: Portfolio, 2022).

Niagara Falls to Buffalo in 1896, and Juneau constructed Alaska's first high-voltage transmission line in the early 1900s, the first transmission lines on the Railbelt were not constructed until the 1920s. The United States played a leading role in testing and deploying high-voltage and ultra-high-voltage transmission lines in the 20th century.³⁹ For the Railbelt, utilities first constructed transmission lines to move power to remote mining load centers or interconnect remote generating assets with low fuel costs, like hydroelectric power. These lines were typically sized just to transfer the needed amount of power, with little margin or redundancy.⁴⁰

The original Eklutna hydroelectric project required 26 miles of transmission line—the second major transmission line on the Railbelt—to transport electricity to Anchorage. The line required 600 power poles and followed the route of the railroad as closely as possible. The 33 kV line was the highest voltage transmission line in the state and permitted all 2 MW of Eklutna generation to flow to Anchorage. The transmission line ran to a substation near the railroad yard, and from there, three feeder lines carried power to the largest consumers in the city: the railroad, the City of Anchorage, and water facilities. AL&P wanted to extend transmission to the Matanuska Valley and out to Willow Creek, but low load expectations, the high cost of crossing the Knik Arm and Matanuska River, and the stock market crash (just after the completion of the project) stopped any expansion.⁴¹ As historian Thomas Hughes argues in his seminal history of electrification, by the 1930s, the development of large interconnected systems had emerged as the expected path of growth.⁴² Even in Alaska, ever-sprawling and increasingly dense electrical connections were the dream *de jure*.

The construction of the railroad allowed Fairbanks to exit its wood famine and switch from burning wood to coal for the majority of its heat and electricity needs. It also drove a revitalization of Fairbanks' economy with industrialized gold mining powered by coal-generated electricity. The Fairbanks Exploration (FE) Company, a subsidiary of the Boston-based US Smelting, Refining, and Mining Company, brought large-scale corporate mining to the region and the need for vast amounts of electricity along with it. The FE Company spent an estimated \$15 million to construct a long-distance water pipeline (the Davidson Ditch), purchase electric dredges from the Union Works plant in San Francisco, and construct a multi-million-dollar power plant before the company ever produced an ounce of gold from dredge operations. The \$1.5 million power plant produced 9.5 MW via modern steam turbines installed by Stevens and Wood of New York City. The turbines generated electricity at 2.3 kV, which was sent to the

Figure 6: Example of standard pole. AL&P Transmission Line Details. From National Archives, Pacific AK Region APA, Box 42.

³⁹ Raymond Lings, "Overview of Transmission Lines Above 700 kV," *IEEE*, 2005.

⁴⁰ Chugach Electric Association, "Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO," 18.

⁴¹ Hollinger, "Early Electrification of Anchorage," 31–33.

⁴² Hughes, *Networks of Power*.

various creeks and stepped down to 440 V.⁴³ This was the largest power plant in Alaska and one of the largest power plants in the circumpolar north at the time.

The FE Company constructed a series of transmission lines to bring this coal-fired electricity from downtown Fairbanks (on Illinois Street, where GVEA is currently headquartered) to its electric dredges in Ester, Fox, and Chatanika. The FE Company's electric transmission system was quite novel. Typically, longer-distance transmission wires were associated with early hydroelectric dams, like Niagara Falls or Eklutna Lake. Coal-fired plants seldom required long transmission lines, as they were built in or near urban centers—the primary sources of electrical load.⁴⁴ In the case of Fairbanks, transmission wires dozens of miles long radiated outward from the city center, from which they powered a constellation of dredges.⁴⁵ When the FE Company's plant and transmission came online, Fairbanks hosted a rather novel "coal-by-wire" distribution system.⁴⁶

Figure 7: "Fairbanks Exploration Company Power Plant, Fairbanks," probably 1933. Source: Special Collections, University of Washington Libraries.

Electric generation and transmission allowed energy from coal to be transferred from downtown Fairbanks to a variety of operations in the Interior. Electricity fueled not only dredges but also draglines and shovels throughout the Interior.⁴⁷ The electrification of Ester, due east of Fairbanks, began after the

⁴³ Clark C. Spence, *The Northern Gold Fleet: The Story of the Twentieth-Century Dredging of the Bering Sea* (Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1999), 81, 111.

⁴⁴ The history of energy and power has structured the nature of urban, suburban, and rural growth since the Industrial Revolution. See David E. Nye, *Electrifying America: Social Meanings of a New Technology, 1880-1940* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1990).

⁴⁵ For this claim about transmission lines in the early 20th century, see Christopher F. Jones, "The Materiality of Energy," *Canadian Journal of History* 53, no. 3 (winter 2018): 386.

⁴⁶ From the perspective of carrying coal power dozens or hundreds of miles, this operation presaged the era of "mine-mouth" coal plants throughout the postwar U.S., including in Healy in 1967.

⁴⁷ In the Yukon, electric shovels were used beginning in 1925 to excavate gravels; see Ken S. Coates and William R. Morrison, *Land of the Midnight Sun: A History of the Yukon* (Montreal, Quebec: McGill-Queens University Press, 2017), 196.

FE Company discovered a gold deposit in 1933 following a deep drilling campaign. Engineers deployed massive hydraulics and a dragline to access the gold-bearing gravel. The FE Company purchased one of the largest draglines in the U.S. at that time, a 750-ton model made by Bucyrus-Mangham that was energized by electrical motors producing about 1,000 horsepower. Electrified Ester operations began a period of successful mining in August 1940 after the FE Company constructed a 7-mile transmission line from its downtown steam plant.⁴⁸

The 1930s witnessed both the height of industrial mining in Alaska and the beginning of Alaska's next economic chapter. As part of a series of nationwide relocation programs to revive the economy, the federal government brought 203 families from the upper Midwest to Alaska's Matanuska Valley in 1935. While the farmers struggled, they established the permanent community of Palmer, a dairy cooperative, and Alaska's first electrical cooperative in 1941: the Matanuska Electric Association (MEA). While the value of gold and gold mining activities reached its zenith in the 1930s, Congressional appropriation of over \$20 million in 1939 and 1940 for military bases throughout the state—especially along the Railbelt in Anchorage and Fairbanks—signaled the start of a new chapter of defense electrification.

II. War and Statehood, 1939 – 1962

The next major phase of Railbelt electrification came with the first global conflict to engulf and militarize the far north—World War II. The war arguably transformed Alaska more than any other single event in Alaskan history. The global conflict was quickly followed by the Cold War, which, especially in its early years (1947–1962), provided one of the single most consequential buildouts of Railbelt generation and transmission. Unsurprisingly, the U.S. military and the federal government dominated this chapter of Railbelt electrification. Between 1940 and 1970, the U.S. military employed more people and spent more money in Alaska than any other entity.⁴⁹

Generation and transmission during this period were characterized by several features. The military built a profusion of generation facilities, nearly all fueled by coal and diesel. The military also invested in coal mining and petroleum development throughout the far north to support allied energy needs in the region. Major new coal heating and power plants were constructed at Fairbanks (FMUS), Ladd Airfield (Fort Wainwright), Eielson Air Force Base, Clear Air Force Base, Ft. Richardson, Elmendorf Air Force Base, and Anchorage (Knik Arm plant). This constituted the single largest buildout of coal-fired generation in the history of Alaska. While these generators were not large by contemporary standards, the number, geography, and significance of these facilities played a formative role in the buildout of the Railbelt grid. At the same time, the military looked for options beyond coal generation. It funded low-voltage transmission lines between its bases in Interior Alaska, advocated for an interconnected Railbelt power pool, supported the development of Railbelt hydroelectric resources by other federal agencies, and invested in Alaska's only terrestrial nuclear power plant.

Beyond the military, the federal government played a crucial role in Railbelt G&T during this period in two key ways. First, through the Bureau of Reclamation, the federal government constructed the largest

⁴⁸ Roy B. Earling, Alaska Mining Hall of Fame Foundation, <https://alaskamininghalloffame.org/inductees/earling.php>, accessed February 18, 2022.

⁴⁹ L. Hummel, "The U.S. Military as Geographical Agent: The Case of Cold War Alaska," *The Geographical Review: The American Geographical Society of New York* (2005).

hydroelectric facility on the Railbelt at that time, the 30 MW Eklutna hydropower project. This project entailed 115 kV transmission lines to Anchorage and Palmer—the highest voltage lines in the state. Second, following the creation of the Rural Electrification Administration in 1935, the federal government supported the growth of rural electric cooperatives. Within a decade of their founding, these cooperatives became the engines of Railbelt electrification and were crucial in building transmission. Between the military and cooperatives, the Railbelt grid expanded well beyond the narrow confines of the railroad corridor for the first time. Perhaps because of these expansive developments, it was during this period that the term “Railbelt” came into popular usage.⁵⁰

The exigencies of World War II brought a torrent of men, materiel, and investment to Alaska. Even before the attack on Pearl Harbor, Congress recognized Alaska’s vulnerability and appropriated tens of millions of dollars for new defense installations, including Fort Richardson in Anchorage and Ladd Field in Fairbanks. Following the attack on Pearl Harbor and the Japanese invasion of the Aleutian Islands in June 1942, defense investment surged in Alaska. The U.S. military constructed 39 major infrastructure projects, including airfields, pipelines, highways, and new bases (many constituted nothing less than self-contained cities). At the height of construction, the military shipped 70,000 tons of supplies and materials to Alaska each month.⁵¹ To sustain military forces and readiness, heat and electricity were in great demand throughout Alaska, but especially at the largest bases along the Railbelt. A lack of civilian power capacity meant the military constructed its own facilities.

Building major steam plants at Ladd Field and Fort Richardson were foundational developments early in the wartime buildup. Ladd Field, the first major defense project of the buildup, was completed in 1941 and contained a 1.5 MW coal-fired heat and power plant. Novel utilidors transported steam and other utilities in underground tunnels between the buildings. In June 1940, the Army began the construction of Fort Richardson in Anchorage, which hosted combat aircraft and became the headquarters of the military in Alaska. The Army constructed a major 6 MW steam CHP plant at Fort Richardson. Ladd and Richardson were the only two Army steam plants in the territory and among the few facilities that provided centralized heating and electricity. Electric power at these facilities was utilized primarily for operating equipment and secondarily for light.⁵²

During World War II, the military’s new airbases and power plants were typically self-contained microgrids and did not include electrical transmission. Yet, Alaska was increasingly connected in other ways during the war: new highways, the first hydrocarbon pipeline system in the far north, and new communication systems. For the first time, the Railbelt became connected by hydrocarbon pipeline and telephone wire with Canada and by road all the way to the Lower 48.⁵³

Significant wartime power developments also occurred at the southern end of the Railbelt on the Kenai Peninsula. Early in the war, military planners realized that the Seward–Portage portion of the railroad was precarious and vulnerable. To add redundancy, the military built a port at the ice-free harbor of

⁵⁰ Google Ngram Viewer, “Alaska Railbelt,” December 13, 2024.

⁵¹ James D. Bush, Jr., “Narrative Report of Alaskan Construction, 1941-1944” (Washington, DC: U.S. Army, 1944), 12–14.

⁵² Joel L. Klein, et al., “World War II in Alaska: A Historic Resources Management Plan,” U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, May 1987, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA196078.pdf>, 2–20.

⁵³ Heath Twitchell, *Northwest Epic: The Building of the Alaska Highway* (New York: St. Martin’s Press, 1992).

Whittier and provided access via a tunnel under glaciated mountains. Electric shovels were the prime movers in constructing two crucial railroad tunnels (a lack of power equipment slowed the building of the Portage Tunnel).⁵⁴ Opened in the spring of 1943, the Port of Whittier proved to be a vital supply line during the war and an important extension of the Railbelt. Additionally, the military recognized the vulnerability of the Port of Seward and constructed a network of defensive positions around Resurrection Bay. The keystone of this system was Fort McGilvray, a self-contained fortification that required power from diesel generators.

In the midst of World War II, the U.S. military moved to diversify its Alaskan energy supplies. The Army gave contracts to two new mines in the Healy area: the Diamond Mine and the Usibelli-Sanford Mine. The latter used a novel technique with tractors to strip mine the local coal. Usibelli and Sanford's Army contract to provide Ladd Airfield with 10,000 tons of coal per year began the most important and long-lasting coal company in Railbelt history.⁵⁵ Usibelli is the only coal mine operating today. With the onslaught of the war, the Alaska Railroad reopened the Eska Mine and operated it until the end of the conflict in 1945 to provide coal to the new Army outposts and airfields built throughout Alaska.⁵⁶ Beginning during these years and intensifying in the postwar period, the U.S. military became Alaska's leading consumer of coal.

The War Department (soon renamed the Department of Defense) recognized Alaska's strategic position and continued to invest in the territory after the end of World War II. The creation of the U.S. Air Force in 1947 proved especially formative for Alaska and its energy development. The Air Force built its own facilities 26 miles outside of Fairbanks (Eielson) and next to Fort Richardson in Anchorage (Elmendorf Field). The Air Force also built a secretive radar and monitoring facility at Clear in the late 1950s. To accommodate these developments, the federal government invested \$100 million in a full-scale rehabilitation of the Alaska Railroad beginning in 1949. The transportation infrastructure had been so worn down that the commander of the U.S. Army in Alaska called it a "470-mile streak of rusting junk" after the war.⁵⁷ In addition to rebuilding the mainline, the government extended it by 26 miles outside of Fairbanks in 1949 to Eielson Air Force Base and rerouted the railroad to accommodate Clear Air Force Station in the late 1950s.⁵⁸

This period of defense electrification built nearly two orders of magnitude more generation than existed on the Railbelt before World War II. The six installations at Richardson, Elmendorf, Clear, Wainwright, Eielson, and Greely all required either new or upgraded electrical generation. The federal government and civilian utilities added 285 MW of generation during this period of military mobilization. The 1950s were the "zenith of military construction in Alaska" according to Army historian Lyman Woodman, with

⁵⁴ Bruce Parham, "Opening of the Whittier Tunnel, 1942-1943," Cook Inlet Historical Society, January 9, 2020, <https://www.cookinlethistoricalociety.org/articles/opening-of-the-whittier-tunnel-1942-1943>, accessed December 1, 2023.

⁵⁵ "UCM History: Usibelli Story," September 8, 1987, <http://www.usibelli.com/history/usibelli-story#:~:text=Coal%20Mine%2C%20Inc.,Usibelli%20Coal%20Mine%2C%20Inc.,of%20the%20Board%20of%20Directors>, accessed February 15, 2022.

⁵⁶ Roy D. Merritt, "Chronicle of Alaska Coal-Mining History" (Alaska Division of Geological and Geophysical Surveys, 1986), 10–11.

⁵⁷ Hummel, "The U.S. Military as Geographical Agent," 49–50.

⁵⁸ W.A. Jacobs and Lyman L. Woodman, *Alaska District, United States Army, Corps of Engineers, 1946-1974: A History* (Washington, DC: Government Printing Office, 1976), 63.

approximately \$1 billion spent between 1951 and 1960.⁵⁹ These power plants were far larger than their prewar predecessors. A single generation facility—for example, Clear Air Force Station’s 22.5 MW coal plant—was as large as the combined total of all the electrical generation facilities built before the war. Every new generation of military technology in the 20th century, with few exceptions, required more power.

The growth of these new Railbelt military bases both helped to expand the burgeoning Railbelt transmission system and facilitated interconnection plans. For the first time in the history of the Railbelt, in the 1950s, the military funded the construction of long-distance electrical transmission to provide redundancy and resiliency to its bases. While hundreds of miles of a relatively low-voltage transmission system linked Wainwright, Eielson, and Greely in the 1950s, islanded generation and the creation of small microgrids—far more than electrical interconnection—defined this period. These islanded military microgrids (all but Ft. Greely constructed along the railroad with access to coal) created a wider and longer template for eventual high-voltage interconnection.

[In kilowatts]

System	Installed generating capacity	Largest generating unit
Ladd Air Force Base.....	29,000	5,000
Eielson Air Force Base.....	15,000	5,000
Fort Greeley.....	3,000	1,000
Golden Valley Electric Association.....	9,500	3,000
City of Fairbanks.....	8,500	5,000
Clear (under construction).....	22,500	7,500
Chatanika (under construction).....	¹ 5,600	5,600

¹ Hydro.

System	Installed generating capacity	Largest generating unit
Elmendorf Air Force Base.....	23,500	7,500
Fort Richardson.....	32,600	4,000
Knik Arm.....	15,400	5,000
Eklutna, U.S. Bureau of Reclamation.....	¹ 30,000	15,000
City of Anchorage.....	6,736	1,100
City of Seward.....	2,525	1,500
Homer Electric Association.....	2,350	600

Figure 8: Installed Railbelt capacity in 1959, northern and southern regions. “Report of Reconnaissance Power Survey of the Greater Anchorage and Fairbanks Area of Alaska,” Technical Inter-Agency Power Group, 1959.

The largest transmission network utilized by the military was between three of its bases in central and eastern Interior Alaska. In the 1950s and 1960s, GVEA extended its network to Delta Junction and Fort Greely. These electrical connections were officially referred to as an “extensive subtransmission system” and likely involved 34.5 kV infrastructure in the 1950s. “The principal use of this military interconnection has been to wheel energy from Fort Wainwright to the other military installations,” according to a 1969

⁵⁹ Jacobs and Woodman, *Alaska District*, 44–45.

Federal Power Survey.⁶⁰ Yet, in the 1950s, military leaders worried about the adequacy of power supply “to meet defense production, military requirements, and other essential uses under full mobilization, and postattack conditions.”⁶¹

To investigate the military’s power needs, a group of officials from the Department of Defense, Federal Power Commission, Office of Civil and Defense Mobilization, and other federal agencies conducted a survey of Alaska’s Railbelt in 1959. The report by this interagency federal power group recommended the construction of transmission and the operation of a power-sharing pool between Anchorage and Fairbanks. Specifically, the report called for immediate planning to construct a transmission line of at least 115 kV to interconnect Anchorage, Fairbanks, and Big Delta. Government and military planners recommended the formation of a power pool to include all systems of the military, the Bureau of Reclamation, municipalities, and electrical cooperatives. The report also proposed that this network would provide an outlet for the “experimental nuclear power plant” being built at Ft. Greely and would provide a future outlet for a mine-mouth coal plant in Healy and a hydroelectric plant planned for the Susitna River.⁶² The report also recommended building larger hydroelectric facilities that “provide incremental capacity that will fit the progressive load growth and development of the power pool.”⁶³

The military worked to reinforce the logistics of its coal and petroleum energy supply, as well as develop less expensive and more resilient non-fossil electrical sources. In addition to the proposed power pool and Fairbanks–Anchorage transmission system, the military constructed Alaska’s first and only terrestrial nuclear reactor. In 1957, the Army announced that Ft. Greely—100 miles southeast of Fairbanks—would host an experimental reactor designated the SM-1A (stationary, medium power, first field type). Army engineers designed the 20 MW reactor to be transported as a package and constructed in the field at remote sites. The reactor first went critical in 1962 and supplied heat and power for Fort Greely and the Interior until 1972. The Army’s SM-1A nuclear power plant occasionally provided power to GVEA members when power disruptions occurred in the GVEA system.⁶⁴

While the northern half of the Railbelt saw the most military generation and transmission development, the southern half of the Railbelt witnessed the most population growth and civilian G&T construction. Alaska quickly grew and by 1950 had 138,000 people—20,000 of whom were defense personnel.⁶⁵ Unlike prewar Alaska, where the largest cities were Juneau and Ketchikan, the vast majority of this growth occurred along the Railbelt. Anchorage grew so quickly following WWII that a government report from 1948 concluded, “Growth has been so rapid in the past few years that an accurate estimate is

⁶⁰ Federal Power Survey, 1969, 74.

⁶¹ “Report of Reconnaissance Power Survey of the Greater Anchorage and Fairbanks Area of Alaska,” Technical Inter-Agency Power Group, 1959, in *Hydroelectric Requirements of Alaska*, Hearings before the Subcommittee on Irrigation and Reclamation of the Committee on Interior and Insular Affairs, U.S. Senate, 86th Congress.

⁶² “Interagency Group Recommends Power Pool,” *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, July 16, 1959.

⁶³ “Report of Reconnaissance Power Survey of the Greater Anchorage and Fairbanks Area of Alaska,” 174.

⁶⁴ Catherine R. Hardee, “The Importance of Being Ancillary: The Cold War Context of Fort Greely, Alaska,” M.A. thesis (Liberty University, 2014), 69.

⁶⁵ U.S. Department of the Interior, *Alaska Power Survey*, 1969, 10.

impossible.”⁶⁶ Between April 1950 and December 1951, Anchorage grew an astounding 51%.⁶⁷ This frenetic growth brought major challenges to the city’s limited power supply.

Anchorage turned to surplus wartime generators to meet the energy demand.⁶⁸ *SS Sacketts Harbor* was a T2 tankship that broke apart 800 miles from Adak after the war. The stern of the ship was towed to Anchorage, beached, and its generators connected to the power grid. From 1946 to 1955, the 3.5 MW oil-fired generators met as much as 55% of the city’s electrical needs. For a brief period, it was the largest civilian generator in Anchorage. The city only stopped utilizing the half-sunk tanker as its main power plant when the new Eklutna hydroelectric plant came online in 1955.⁶⁹

Beyond the military, the federal government played a formative role in this period of Railbelt electrical development through the Bureau of Reclamation and rural electric cooperatives. In the postwar era, the federal government saw hydroelectric power as a low-cost, reliable, and clean energy resource for Alaskan growth and development. The Bureau of Reclamation conducted extensive hydroelectric power surveys in the 1950s and 1960s and identified 252 sites for potential projects.⁷⁰ The federal government also conducted pioneering studies of other Alaskan renewable energy sources, notably wind. A 1955 study of the “remarkably high frequency of strong surface winds” in Big Delta presaged the development of the first MW-scale wind development in the early 21st century.⁷¹

The Bureau of Reclamation and other federal agencies did not just study possible sites; they also built two key federal hydroelectric plants in Alaska. The first and only facility on the Railbelt utilized the best hydropower potential near Anchorage—Eklutna Lake.⁷² In 1950, Congress passed the Eklutna Act, which authorized the construction of an expanded facility at a cost of \$20 million.⁷³ The project consisted of a low dam that raised the height of Eklutna Lake by 2 feet and a 4.5-mile tunnel to deliver water down a 1,250-foot penstock to two large generators at the base of the mountains. When it came online in 1955, the Eklutna hydropower facility had both the single largest generating unit (15 MW) and soon the largest total output of any generator in Alaska (30 MW).⁷⁴ It was eventually upgraded to 44 MW. The plant continues to operate and provides the cheapest power on the Railbelt—about 1 cent per kWh.⁷⁵

⁶⁶ Joseph M. Morgan, “Eklutna Project, Alaska: Report of the Chief of Alaska Investigations Office and Substantiating Materials,” U.S. Department of Reclamation, 1948, 2, <https://eklutnahydro.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/USBR-1948-Eklutna-Project-Report-2.pdf>, accessed December 13, 2024.

⁶⁷ Sandberg, “A History of Alaska Population Settlement,” 14.

⁶⁸ This was a common practice in Alaska and Canada. See Alex Souchen, *War Junk: Munitions Disposal and Postwar Reconstruction in Canada* (University of British Columbia Press, 2020).

⁶⁹ Claus-M. Naske and William R. Hunt, “The Politics of Hydroelectric Power in Alaska: Rampart and Devil Canyon: A Case Study” (Fairbanks: Institute of Water Resources, 1978), 51.

⁷⁰ “Energy Policy Report: Program Organization, Division of Policy,” Alaska State Archives, Office of the Governor, October 1987, 7.

⁷¹ J. Murray Mitchell Jr, “Strong Surface Winds at Big Delta, Alaska: An Example of Orographic Influence on Local Weather,” *Monthly Weather Review*, January 1956.

⁷² The second federal hydroelectric facility was the 78 MW Snettisham project 28 miles south of Juneau, constructed by the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers.

⁷³ John Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska: Anchorage, Juneau, Ketchikan, and Sitka* (Fairbanks AK: Institute of Water Resources, 1983), 93.

⁷⁴ Morgan, “Eklutna Project, Alaska.”

⁷⁵ McMillen, Jacobs & Associates, “Eklutna Hydroelectric Project: Revised Draft Study Plans,” January 2021.

Transmission for Eklutna constituted the most advanced and high-voltage transmission system in the Territory at that time. Original plans called for two lines between 115 kV and 161 kV, with one line connecting the generating station to Anchorage and the other heading north 12 miles to Palmer-Wasilla Road. Ultimately, 44 miles of 115 kV transmission lines were constructed from the new Eklutna plant to carry its electricity to Palmer and Anchorage. Engineers planned the transmission system “with a view to incorporating them into a future Seward-Fairbanks backbone transmission line.”⁷⁶ This 115 kV transmission system of hydro lines became the “original backbone transmission system” for MEA and CEA.⁷⁷

Due to the booming population of Anchorage, two years before Eklutna came online, its entire electrical output was already allocated. Former Alaska Territorial Governor Ernest Gruening argued that Alaska and the Railbelt needed far more power, which was why the Bureau of Reclamation was looking at damming the Susitna River and producing an estimated 400,000 kWh. Gruening noted this would produce power at less than 10 mills and make it available “for 200 miles on either side of the Railbelt.” Once again, Alaskans envisioned a large hydroelectric generating source would be the catalyst for the electrical integration of the Railbelt. Gruening, ever the advocate of statehood, reminded his audience: “The representation of two senators and a voting representative would greatly improve the chances of realizing such a project.”⁷⁸

In the mid-1950s, the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) began competing with the Bureau of Reclamation to bring hydroelectric power to Alaska. USACE foresaw building a 46 MW facility at Bradley Lake near Homer (the final project was over twice that size and built by the State of Alaska).⁷⁹ Projected demand remained a major challenge for USACE in 1955, and they investigated constructing an ammonium nitrate facility on the Kenai Peninsula to utilize excess power from the hydro facility.⁸⁰ Alaska’s Territorial Governor Frank Heintzleman speculated in 1957 that Alaska’s Railbelt utilities should come together to realize the Bradley project if they wanted to reap its benefits.⁸¹

Federal representatives and agencies were far from alone in seeing large hydroelectric plants as the economic future of the Railbelt and the state. Alaskan leaders in the 1950s and 1960s expressed a bipartisan commitment to resource development via megaproject development. Even though the vast majority of these projects were never realized, they became important for the buildout of Railbelt generation and transmission in several ways. These projects epitomized the Alaskan belief in rapid economic development via megaprojects. Each project was so large that it demanded an interconnected Railbelt grid (and often beyond, to Copper Valley and, at times, Canada and the Lower 48). These projects clearly articulated the pattern that new generation sources defined the buildout of Railbelt transmission.

⁷⁶ Morgan, “Eklutna Project, Alaska,” 24.

⁷⁷ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on Alaska Railbelt USO,” 19.

⁷⁸ Ernest Gruening, “Alaska: Progress and Problems,” *The Scientific Monthly* 77, no. 1 (July 1953): 10–11.

⁷⁹ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 94–95.

⁸⁰ Carl Farrell to Frank Heintzleman, April 7, 1955, Box VS 837. Alaska State Archives.

⁸¹ Frank Heintzleman Memo, March 28, 1957. Box VS 827. Alaska State Archives.

While the details of these projects are beyond the scope of this study, and most have already been analyzed by historians, three never-constructed projects are worth mentioning: Rampart Dam, Wood Canyon Dam, and Susitna Dam.⁸²

The proposal to dam the Yukon River at Rampart is arguably the most infamous of these hydroelectric megaprojects. In 1959, USACE proposed the massive hydroelectric facility—the largest in the world—where a 470-foot dam would stop North America’s mightiest river and create a reservoir larger than Lake Erie. The massive new lake was so large that it would take 20 years to fill and moderate the climate of Interior Alaska. Inspired by mega hydro projects in Russia and Scandinavia, USACE advised that power could be sent via ultra-high voltage to Seward, Anchorage, and Valdez.⁸³ The project ultimately collapsed under its own weight: not only was there no viable market for its tremendous power output, but an uprising from conservationists and the Athabascan peoples of Yukon Flats (where the reservoir would drown numerous villages) killed the project. It officially died in 1971.

Competition between the Bureau of Reclamation and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers encouraged the former to investigate the hydropower potential of the Susitna River. In 1952, Joseph M. Morgan of the Alaska Office of the Bureau of Reclamation published a 168-page report advocating for multiple dams and hydropower facilities throughout the Susitna Basin. The “Morgan Plan,” as some called it, envisioned 11 power plants totaling 1.25 GW, beginning with a 390 MW facility at Devil’s Canyon. “This report can be to Alaska what the first Columbia River 308 report of December 1932 was to the Pacific Northwest,” one book review in the *Public Power Bulletin* argued, concluding that “it will be a great day for Alaska when the first blast heralds the beginning of construction of Devil Canyon Dam.”⁸⁴

Crucially, to transmit all this power, the report called for a 230 kV “backbone transmission system” from Fairbanks to Anchorage, with lower voltage lines throughout the Kenai Peninsula (Figure 9). Submarine cables would be utilized to cross the Knik Arm (which would be finally realized in 1968 with the Beluga transmission). In justifying this expansive system, the report noted that Chugach and Golden Valley were already expanding their transmission lines to Portage and Big Delta, respectively, to provide needed power to rural regions.⁸⁵ If anyone could deliver a high-voltage system for Alaska’s Railbelt in the 1950s, it was the federal government. From 1934 to 1952, the United States operated the only 230 kV or higher transmission system in the world—the 287 kV lines from Hoover Dam to Los Angeles.⁸⁶ The 1952 Susitna “backbone transmission vision” and corresponding map constitute perhaps the first map of an integrated Railbelt grid—one that featured the still-elusive goal of a 230 kV transmission system.

⁸² Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*; Naske and Hunt, “The Politics of Hydroelectric Power in Alaska.”

⁸³ Naske and Hunt, “The Politics of Hydroelectric Power in Alaska.”

⁸⁴ *Public Power Bulletin*, 7, Book Review: Susitna River.

⁸⁵ Joseph M. Morgan, “Susitna River Basin: A Report on Potential Development of Water Resources in the Susitna River Basin of Alaska” Bureau of Reclamation (August 1952), 58–59.

⁸⁶ Lings, “Overview of Transmission Lines Above 700 kV,” 34.

Figure 9: "Federal Generation and Transmission Facilities Proposed and Under Construction (Excludes Military)." Source: Joseph M. Morgan, "Susitna River Basin: A Report on Potential Development of Water Resources in the Susitna River Basin of Alaska," Bureau of Reclamation, August 1952

Alaska’s young rural electric cooperatives aimed to build their own interconnected hydropower grid in the 1950s. Chugach Electric Association and a proposed G&T cooperative called the Central Alaska Power Association (CAPA) were interested in developing a large hydroelectric facility at Wood Canyon on the Copper River.⁸⁷ Harvey Aluminum originally requested a preliminary permit as part of a larger plan to smelt aluminum with hydroelectric power from the site. CAPA took over the project in September 1956 by applying for a preliminary federal permit and agreeing to furnish 240,000 kW to Harvey Aluminum if developed. The preliminary proposal envisioned a concrete dam 560 feet high, creating a 51-mile reservoir up the Copper River and developing a power plant capable of generating 1.1 GW.⁸⁸ The *Anchorage Daily News* supported this development, heralding “Wood Canyon is for all of US” in a 1954 article.⁸⁹ Despite initial enthusiasm and a confirmed industrial customer, the dam proposal immediately alarmed fishermen and never moved beyond the planning stage.

Even more important than these federal hydroelectric projects was the realization of a new public organization for electrifying Alaska and America—the rural electric cooperative. Between 1935 and 1936, President Franklin Delano Roosevelt and the U.S. Congress signed executive orders and legislation that provided federal loans and support for rural electric cooperatives. The Rural Electrification Administration (REA) provided these crucial loans and helped rural communities set up their own rural electric cooperatives. Alaskan farmers responded by asking for the organization of MEA in 1937. The REA approved MEA’s organization in 1941, and Alaska’s first cooperative began distributing electrical power from the Eklutna hydroelectric facility to 127 members in 1942 when it completed a 33 kV transmission line from Eklutna to Palmer.⁹⁰ MEA proved to be an important exemplar for other communities between Fairbanks and Homer, as well as elsewhere in the Territory.⁹¹

Matanuska Electric Association (MEA)	1941
Golden Valley Electric Association (GVEA)	1946
Chugach Electric Association (CEA)	1948
Homer Electric Association (HEA)	1945 (Homer), 1950 (Kenai)

Figure 10: Founding of Railbelt rural electric cooperatives.

Alaska’s new cooperatives wasted no time building new generation and interconnecting their regions with low-cost financing from the federal government. These REA projects brought online significant non-military generation and transmission between 1945 and 1961. REA investment in Alaska more than tripled to \$154 million between 1959 and 1969. In the 1950s, most of this funding was directed at Anchorage and Fairbanks.⁹²

⁸⁷ “Cooperative Meets City Rates in Mt. View, Spenard, Fairview,” *Chugach Current* 8, no. 6 (September 1956).

⁸⁸ “CAPA Asks Dam Permit,” *Anchorage Daily Times*, September 29, 1956.

⁸⁹ “Wood Canyon is for all of US,” *Anchorage Daily News*, 1954.

⁹⁰ 1941 agreement with AL&P and MEA to provide 250 kWh; MEA built a 33 kV transmission line to Palmer with a low-interest REA loan (2.46%).

⁹¹ Patti Harper, “Northern Lights: A History of Alaska’s Electric Cooperatives” (Anchorage: AT Publishing, 1994), 5–6.

⁹² Ross Coen, “How Rural Electricity Empowered Alaska’s Politics,” *Anchorage Daily News*, 2012.

Figure 11: Chugach Electric Association's Knik Arm coal-fired steam CHP plant on Ship Creek, 1953. Source: *First Annual Report, Chugach Electric Association, 1953.*

Anchorage offered an ideal location to send power to population centers both north and south, and Chugach foresaw enormous growth for electrification beyond Anchorage. In 1953, Chugach Electric Association (CEA) began selling power to Matanuska Electric Association along the existing 33 kV Eklutna hydro lines, beginning a long-standing practice whereby Chugach became the wholesale power provider for many of Alaska's Railbelt coops.⁹³

Less than five years old, Chugach began consolidating to accomplish electric growth and drive down the cost of power. The Alaska Railroad constructed a coal-fired steam plant between 1949 and 1951 called the Knik Arm power plant that was jointly owned by CEA. Its first 3 MW turbine came online in 1953 and eventually produced 11.5 MW.⁹⁴ The cogeneration plant produced steam for both the Railroad and CEA, with roughly 85% of its output designated for electricity, mostly for Chugach. The rapid growth of Anchorage meant Chugach needed more power, so it purchased the plant from the Alaska Railroad and took over operations on December 1, 1953.⁹⁵ In 1955, the Knik Arm plant purchased over \$341,000

⁹³ Harper, "Northern Lights"; Chugach Electric Association, *First Annual Report*, 1953.

⁹⁴ Chugach Electric Association, *First Annual Report*, 1953.

⁹⁵ FE Kalbach, General Manager, to William S. Strand, Director, "AKRR Correspondence, Chugach Electric," Folder: AKRR Correspondence, Box 9242, Alaska Railroad Corporation, Alaska State Archives.

worth of coal from Matanuska miners to generate heat and power.⁹⁶ In 1954, Chugach also bought out the Inlet Power and Light Company, which had about 2.8 MW of diesel generation, and began expanding transmission.⁹⁷

Consolidating generation and setting up power pools emerged as cutting-edge features of the electric utility industry in the 1940s. Throughout World War II, system operators built and organized larger and larger integrated networks that could supply essential electricity to defense industries. The Northwest Power Pool was an important example: during the war, federal hydroelectric dams, rural cooperatives, and investor-owned and municipal utilities in five states came together and effectively coordinated an installed capacity of 4.5 million horsepower (33 GW). By the 1960s, dozens of power pools existed throughout the nation.⁹⁸ It was in this historic context that Railbelt power pooling efforts began.

The 1950s witnessed a formative but failed attempt to create a Railbelt generation and transmission cooperative. In the mid-1950s, Chugach, Matanuska, Homer, and Kenai electric associations (the Homer and Kenai REA utilities later merged) formed the Central Alaska Power Association (CAPA) for the purpose of developing “cheap Kenai hydro.” Membership of the G&T cooperative was open to municipal and private utilities, but only cooperatives joined. The CAPA Board comprised members of the CEA, MEA, and HEA Boards. The purpose of CAPA was to create a power pool, develop cheap power generation—especially “dump power rates” from hydroelectric—and reduce costs. Both the City of Seward and Anchorage’s Chamber of Commerce (whose power committee was headed by a young developer named Wally Hickel) supported the creation and mission of CAPA.⁹⁹ Beyond the Kenai, CAPA members were also interested in the prospective Wood Canyon hydro dam on the Copper River, which would distribute power all over the Railbelt, as well as to Cordova and Valdez.¹⁰⁰

Friction over the venture quickly emerged and doomed the Railbelt’s first G&T cooperative. Although it accomplished tangible work by doing engineering studies on Cooper Lake hydroelectric, applying for REA loans, and filing preliminary permits with the Federal Power Commission, the G&T cooperative stumbled in the face of widespread resistance. In Homer, Anchorage, and the Matanuska Valley, critics charged CAPA with a variety of offenses.

The *Homer News* opined against the poor transparency and questionable financial dealings at CAPA and warned readers: “It’s your money, but it isn’t any of your business how it is being spent.” The newspaper concluded: “We want public power. We want cheap power. But we also want sound administration, public administration that isn’t afraid to tell the public the facts of life.” An overriding concern from critical journalists was that “Public power is no longer public.”¹⁰¹

In Anchorage, friction between the Chugach Electric Association and the Municipality of Anchorage fueled additional discontent. In the late 1950s, each proposed purchasing the other to end ongoing

⁹⁶ “Cooperative Meets City Rates in Mt. View, Spenard, Fairview.”

⁹⁷ Morgan, “Susitna River Basin,” 51.

⁹⁸ Cohen, “When the Grid was a Grid.”

⁹⁹ “Schultz to Head Big Co-Op,” *Homer News*, December 16, 1954.

¹⁰⁰ “Cooperative Meets City Rates in Mt. View, Spenard, Fairview.” CAPA filed for a preliminary Federal Power permit (No. 2015) for the Wood Canyon Project, see public notice, *Anchorage Daily Times*, December 3, 1956.

¹⁰¹ “Public Power No. 3,” *The Homer News*, July 28, 1955.

struggles over duplicate services and the electric future of the Anchorage region. They fought over two central questions: who would drive electric growth in the region, and who would provide electric service to whom? The development of Cooper Lake hydropower by CAPA in the late 1950s was a flashpoint in this larger turf battle. In a 1956 newspaper spread, Chugach boasted about its accomplishments and communicated with Anchorageites about the “foes” of CAPA. “City Hall is determined to run Chugach out of town and take over 3,200 of its members. If City Hall would leave Chugach alone, many thousands of customers from Homer to Anchorage to Palmer would have Cooper Lake within three years...and the cheapest power rates in the territory.”¹⁰² Yet, southcentral cooperatives including CEA killed a 1959–1960 federal bill that would have raised the height of the Eklutna dam (with the goal of creating stable year-round power) because it would have given the municipality of Anchorage discounted electrical rates.¹⁰³

Perhaps the greatest drama occurred in the Matanuska Valley. A series of fractious battles over MEA’s involvement in CAPA led to a civil war on the board, lawsuits, board resignations, and a crisis at Alaska’s oldest electrical cooperative. Contentious issues included a murky \$15,000 loan, financial transparency at CAPA, the future of MEA’s power supply, whether MEA should be more than a distribution cooperative, and whether membership should vote on that issue.¹⁰⁴ One MEA board member resigned over MEA’s involvement with CAPA, precipitating a battle between MEA board members and resulting in multiple lawsuits. “No matter how much such an organization is needed in Alaska,” Board Member Wilson wrote in a public resignation letter, “I cannot be a willing party to such management.” Behind the civil war over CAPA were questions about the future of MEA, including whether power would continue to come from hydropower or pivot toward more coal-fired steam generation.

In May 1957, the Chugach Board of Directors narrowly voted 4-to-3 after two hours of bitter debate to withdraw from CAPA. Newspapers reported that Chugach, the largest member and driving force of CAPA, “has chosen to go it alone since it is the largest cooperative in the area and the only one financially capable of building the controversial Cooper Lake [hydroelectric] project.”¹⁰⁵ Chugach’s withdrawal effectively killed CAPA, with Chugach moving forward on its own to build, own, and operate the Kenai Peninsula transmission system and 16 MW hydropower project at Cooper Lake. In a move that profoundly shaped the future of the Railbelt, Chugach emerged as the region’s wholesale power supplier on its own—not as part of a larger Railbelt G&T cooperative.

Chugach mobilized all its resources to energize Cooper Lake hydroelectric and its hydro lines. As early as 1953, Chugach recognized its new Knik Arm plant and the soon-to-be-operational Eklutna hydro plant were already fully subscribed. “We must look elsewhere,” Chugach concluded in its first annual report in 1953; “The consensus of all engineering talent is that the Kenai Peninsula presents a number of small and medium hydro sites which can be economically developed.”¹⁰⁶ To bring this power to Anchorage, CEA needed over 100 miles of transmission lines across the rocky shores of Turnagain Arm and mountain passes of the Kenai Peninsula. Chugach obtained a \$12.5 million REA loan and, by 1958,

¹⁰² “What is Chugach Electric’s Contribution to the Greater Community,” *Anchorage Daily Times*, July 21, 1956, 4–5.

¹⁰³ E.L.B. Papers, 86th Congress, Legislative Bill File, Box 9, S 3222, Eklutna Power Project, 1959–1960.

¹⁰⁴ “Wilson to Resign from MEA Board,” *The Frontiersman*, March 29, 1956, 1, 8.

¹⁰⁵ “Territorial News Items,” *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, May 16, 1957.

¹⁰⁶ Chugach Electric Association, *First Annual Report*, 1953.

energized the first part of a 50-mile transmission line to Portage (in early 1957, this transmission was called the “CAPA line”).¹⁰⁷

Figure 12: “1955-1961, View looking Southwest near Homer, Alaska.” UAA Archives.

Chugach completed the Cooper Lake hydroelectric plant in 1960 but experienced major delays in getting the transmission lines approved and built. In May 1961, the line came online to serve Homer, and in June, the line was completed to serve Moose Pass and Seward. However, CEA ran into trouble with the Forest Service for their Johnson Pass powerline through the Chugach National Forest to serve Anchorage. The U.S. Forest Service opposed the power line for “aesthetic reasons.” Chugach, in turn, opposed the Forest Service route because of concerns about avalanches, snow conditions, maintenance accessibility, and higher costs. Power did not begin to flow to Anchorage until 1962.¹⁰⁸ Originally, this transmission line only moved 16 MW from the Cooper Lake hydroelectric facility; over time, it was upgraded (it can now move 75 MW) and became the crucial connection between Anchorage and the Kenai.¹⁰⁹

Chugach’s interconnection of hydro lines from Cooper Lake to Seward, Homer, and Anchorage constituted an important milestone in Railbelt G&T history. These 69 kV transmission lines, combined with the Bureau of Reclamation’s 115 kV system, created a small regional electric grid capable of some reserve sharing and limited transfers of power.¹¹⁰ “By 1960 it appeared as if Chugach was in a position to challenge the federal government as the principal hydro producer in Anchorage—unless Rampart, Devil Canyon or Bradley Lake were built,” noted Alaska hydroelectric historian John Whitehead.¹¹¹ During these years, CEA also pursued a 10 MW hydro facility at Grant Lake on the Kenai. Despite decades of work, this power plant has yet to be constructed. During these decades, the Anchorage load center stretched 45 miles north to the Matanuska-Susitna valley, 127 miles south to Seward, and eventually

¹⁰⁷ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 95.

¹⁰⁸ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 95.

¹⁰⁹ Alaska Energy Authority, “Railbelt Transmission Plan,” March 6, 2017, 3.

¹¹⁰ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 19.

¹¹¹ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 95.

226 miles to Homer.¹¹² The importance of this new transmission system became clear when Railbelt methane gas generation first came online at Bernice Lake north of Kenai in 1962 and began to provide “gas by wire” to Anchorage. Despite these major advancements, neither the federal government nor the Railbelt’s cooperatives managed to interconnect the Railbelt by linking Fairbanks and Anchorage.

III. Gassing Up, 1962–1984

Alaska’s Railbelt utilities experienced phenomenal load and transmission growth during the 1960s and 1970s. The electrification boom commenced in the 1960s and dramatically increased with the pipeline boom of the 1970s. New generation during this period was predominately oil and methane gas. It was Alaska’s petroleum boom in more ways than one, as the discovery of Swanson River and Prudhoe Bay led to oil and gas exports as well as increased electrical generation from indigenous fossil resources. Yet, as the Railbelt became ever more interconnected, the underlying energy sources powering this growth became more volatile and precarious with the oil crises of the 1970s.

Between 1962 and 1984, Railbelt entities brought online over 1.2 GW of additional generation—over five times as much as the prior period. With an average yearly addition of over 56 MW, this period saw the largest growth of nameplate capacity in the history of the Railbelt. Unlike the prior military period, coops and municipal utilities constructed the bulk of this generation. Civilian and commercial growth was now fueling Alaska’s economy.

During this period, Railbelt utilities continued their buildout of regional transmission lines. The pipeline boom resulted in a second wave of cooperative-owned transmission (the first being between 1942 and 1961). This expanded transmission system offered numerous benefits, including a broader demand base and more optimally sized generation plants. Increased interconnection also allowed reserve capacity to be a smaller portion of total system capacity and allowed a smaller portion of capacity to be allocated for peaking.

The discovery of oil at Swanson River in 1957 and the subsequent discovery of methane gas were major turning points for Alaska’s generation and transmission development. Gas emerged as a strong competitor to coal and hydropower and eventually became the dominant fuel of the Railbelt by the 1970s. As early as 1960, CEA noted that gas power might cost as little as 5 mills per kWh, less than half of the 11 mills per kWh from Eklutna.¹¹³ In 1962, the first gas turbine produced electricity for Anchorage when CEA began operating a plant at Bernice Lake, near Nikiski on the Kenai Peninsula.¹¹⁴ Two units at Bernice Lake eventually came online that year, providing 25 MW—the largest single steam or thermal generation plant on the Railbelt at that time. The availability of oil and gas in the Anchorage Bowl also led to fuel switching, where military and civilian power plants converted from coal to gas for their steam plants. By 1965, Chugach had installed 37.5 MW, and Anchorage Municipal Light and Power had installed 30 MW of gas generation.¹¹⁵

¹¹² Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 85.

¹¹³ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 98.

¹¹⁴ John Whitehead says 1963, other sources say 1962. Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 98.

¹¹⁵ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 98.

Chugach faced a choice between gas and hydroelectric generation in the early 1960s, which impacted CEA's wholesale power customers, HEA and MEA. With rapid growth in the 15 years between 1961 and 1976, Chugach grew more than 1,000%. Low-cost Cook Inlet gas proved competitive with hydroelectric on an operational basis, and gas did not have the high upfront capital costs of hydropower. The REA more easily provided loans for Chugach to build gas generation than more expensive hydro projects. Major hydroelectric projects like Rampart, Susitna, or Bradley Lake also required Congressional approval and appropriations. If Chugach had pursued this hydro route, they would not have owned the generation but would have just purchased and distributed the power, as they did with the Eklutna project. "Gas provided Chugach the attractive possibility to emerge as not only the largest distributor of electric power in Anchorage, but also the largest producer," historian John Whitehead concludes. "Gas gave Chugach an independence it probably would not have gained if hydro had become the major source of power in Anchorage."¹¹⁶ As with so much of the Railbelt's G&T history, the cost of generation was only one important factor amongst many.

Gas generation continued to expand with the discovery and development of the large Beluga River field. The construction of the remote Beluga power station on the west side of Cook Inlet proved to be an impressive logistical operation, as the facility was not connected to the road system and required resupply by air and sea.¹¹⁷ CEA began producing power at Beluga in 1968 with a 32 MW generator, the single largest generator in the state. Beluga River units 1 and 2 came online in 1968 with just under 40 MW of capacity. Four more units added a whopping 290 MW between 1973 and 1978 as Alaska's population and electricity needs exploded with the pipeline boom. The 385 MW plant later housed eight turbines and became the largest in the state.¹¹⁸

In addition to the size and capacity of the Beluga plant, its location proved economically beneficial but logistically challenging from the perspective of transmission. The Beluga generating facility was sited adjacent to one of the largest gas fields in the Cook Inlet (discovered in 1961 by Standard Oil of California). By the late 1960s, numerous studies found that transmitting electrons via high-voltage transmission lines to load centers was less expensive than moving gas via pipeline or coal via rail to a generating plant closer to load centers.¹¹⁹ As one U.S. Senate staffer phrased it, in Alaska, "there is plenty of gas and coal in reasonably convenient locations."¹²⁰ This economic dynamic also had social benefits, as large point sources of pollution from thermal generation were moved away from population centers. Yet, Chugach faced numerous challenges and issues in constructing Beluga's transmission lines, which required underwater cables between Pt. MacKenzie and Woronzof (and between the east and west terminals under Knik Arm).¹²¹ Additional transmission lines—eventually totaling three 230 kV lines—were built as new Beluga generation units came online in the 1970s.

Questions of efficiency, duplication, and effective power pooling were common in the 1950s and 1960s. From Fairbanks to Anchorage, public officials recognized the fundamental inefficiencies of the Railbelt's

¹¹⁶ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 99–100.

¹¹⁷ "O&M Staff Keep Their Cool at Alaska Plant," *Power*, March 15, 2006, <https://www.powermag.com/om-staff-keep-their-cool-at-alaskan-plant/>, accessed December 29, 2024.

¹¹⁸ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 99.

¹¹⁹ U.S. Department of the Interior, *Alaska Power Survey, 1969*, 42.

¹²⁰ Dan Dreyfus to Jerry Verkler, "Annual Report: Alaska Power Administration," February 7, 1969.

¹²¹ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 106.

postwar power system and sought to modernize the system, namely via transmission and power pooling. “The power problem in Alaska is that small, widely scattered load centers have had to develop expedient, inefficient, and uneconomic generation,” concluded U.S. Senator Henry Jackson’s legislative staffer. So backward was Alaska’s system, he quipped that “In many Alaskan towns...you cannot use an electric clock or electric razor effectively.” While the federal government had been envisioning and advocating for a Railbelt electric grid centered around a large hydroelectric facility since the late 1940s, by the late 1960s, federal officials recognized that while sources of generation might be different, the need for transmission remained. “If these [widely-scattered] loads were tied together by a transmission grid, they could be served from large, dependable economic plants—probably non-federal thermal plants.” Load growth permitting, a large federal hydroelectric plant could be added to the system.¹²²

State officials often agreed with this federal assessment. In forwarding this 1969 Federal Power Study to Governor Walter Hickel, Alaska’s Commissioner of the Department of Commerce noted that the cheapest sources of Railbelt generation were Beluga Gas and a major hydroelectric installation (either Susitna or Bradley Lake). However, such low costs were reliant on a transmission line from Fairbanks to Homer to “connect the whole rail belt area.” This would require “all utilities interconnecting their systems so that the most efficient generation could be used for all users and the reserves required reduced to a minimum.” This would require the integration of Chugach and ML&P—two rival utilities that often fought over issues of duplication.¹²³

The 9.2 magnitude 1964 Alaska Earthquake—the largest ever recorded in North America—caused extensive damage to the power system in southcentral Alaska but also revealed the benefits of a grid fueled by generators in diverse geographies. The Fort Richardson, Elmendorf, and Knik Arm steam plants all suffered significant damage, as did the intake of the Eklutna Lake hydropower facility. An earthquake-caused avalanche disrupted the 115 kV transmission line between Eklutna and Palmer, causing an outage for 18 hours in the Matanuska Valley. Other than vibration damage to turbines at Bernice Lake, neither that plant nor the Cooper Lake hydropower facility suffered major damage. Transmission lines were perhaps the most impacted. Avalanches destroyed several towers between Portage and Cooper Lake and between Cooper Lake and Seward. The transmission line along Turnagain Arm, particularly between Girdwood and Portage, suffered the most damage. This section was severely affected by “gigantic translatory landslides,” with 13 towers demolished and another 60 requiring extensive repairs. Ironically, the Sterling–Quartz (SQ) line that would prove most problematic during the 21st century had power restored within 1.5 hours and powered Soldotna.¹²⁴

While damage was widespread, the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) reported that much of the damage to transmission lines was not unlike that which often occurred during Alaskan winters. The Geological Survey also reported that while the damage to the grid was “disastrous and expensive, the power system failures were fortuitous” insofar as the power was immediately severed to Anchorage; therefore, there was almost a complete lack of fires.¹²⁵ The northern reaches of the Railbelt north of the Alaska

¹²² Dreyfus to Verkler, “Annual Report: Alaska Power Administration.”

¹²³ Chad C. Moore to Governor Walter Hickel, October 16, 1968.

¹²⁴ Edwin B. Eckel, “The Alaska Earthquake: Effects on Transportation and Utilities,” *Geological Survey Professional Paper 545-B* (1967): B19–B21. For information on the SQ line, see Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 104.

¹²⁵ Eckel, “The Alaska Earthquake,” B19–B21.

Range were spared widespread damage but faced ongoing challenges with modernizing generation and transmission.

In Interior Alaska, GVEA moved forward with plans to construct its first generation plant. During the first years of operation, GVEA relied on purchased power from the FE Company’s 9.5 MW plant and a private 5.6 MW hydropower project on the Chatanika River (from 1959 until 1967). While GVEA eventually purchased the FE Company plant in 1952, they knew it had a limited lifespan; the plant served Fairbanks for 41 years (1927–1968). While early plans called for a nuclear reactor in Fairbanks, REA refused to offer a loan for the project, citing its risky nature.¹²⁶ Instead, GVEA moved forward with a mine-mouth coal plant at Healy. The *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner* reported on a plan for the Healy coal power plant and its transmission infrastructure—including a never-constructed line stretching across the Alaska Range foothills between Healy and Big Delta—in 1957.¹²⁷

Figure 13: Envisioned interior transmission, *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, December 30, 1957.

¹²⁶ Philip A. Wight, “Nuclear Currents: The U.S. Military and Nuclear Power in the Alaska Pacific,” in *An American Lake? The United States, War and Environment in the Recent Pacific World*. Eds. Beth Baily, Andrew Isenberg, and Paul Landsberg (Lawrence, KS: University of Kansas Press, 2025) (forthcoming).

¹²⁷ *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, December 30, 1957.

Alaskans had long looked to the coal reserves at Healy for energy and power. When famed Alaskan geologist Alfred Brooks explored the Healy area in 1902, he suggested that one day, a power plant should be constructed there to utilize the coal reserves. The idea had been discussed throughout the years, especially after mining began in 1918, and the idea was realized in the 1960s with the Interior's growing electric needs.¹²⁸ With REA funds in hand, GVEA moved forward with its 25 MW coal plant at Healy (later known as Healy 1). The plant came online in 1967 and still operates today as one of GVEA's lowest-cost and most reliable (albeit highest carbon) sources of power.

In 1967, GVEA completed a crucial 138 kV transmission line between Healy and Fairbanks that permitted Healy

coal power to be transmitted to Interior Alaska's population and load center. At the time, this was the highest voltage transmission line in the state (a distinction eclipsed a year later by the 230 kV lines from Beluga to Anchorage). "The ability of transmission wires to deliver electricity cheaply, abundantly, and reliably," energy historian Christopher Jones argues, "rendered the distance between sites of production and consumption negligible."¹²⁹ The 1967 line continues to operate at 138 kV, transmitting coal, wind, hydro, and gas-fired generation to Fairbanks.

The 1968 discovery of oil at Prudhoe Bay—the largest conventional oil field in North America—forever changed Alaska's energy development. For the purposes of this study, the discovery of Prudhoe Bay and subsequent efforts to construct the Trans-Alaska Pipeline System (TAPS) transformed the Railbelt in four ways. First, it offered a possible but unrealized avenue for building a pipeline electrical grid between Fairbanks and the Copper River Valley, with an eventual link to Anchorage. Second, it effectively doubled the state's population and dramatically increased electrical demand. Third, it entrenched oil-fired generation in Interior Alaska at precisely the moment when the rest of the United States was rapidly moving away from petroleum-generated electricity. Finally, it transformed the state from one of the poorest to one of the richest in the Union, with ample funds for infrastructural investments (see the next section on oil and water).

Figure 14: "A View looking down the GVEA transmission line, 1967." UAF Archives.

¹²⁸ Beverley Hall Mitchell, "Healy History," self-published, n.d., 14.

¹²⁹ Jones, *Routes of Power*, 179.

With the discovery of Prudhoe Bay and the announcement of TAPS, Alaska’s electric utilities saw an opportunity to grow and interconnect their systems. GVEA, HEA, MEA, and the Copper Valley Electric Association (CVEA) formed the non-profit Trans-Alaska Electric Generation and Transmission Cooperative to take advantage of this “unusual opportunity” for the “coincident development of...an electric power system.” The Trans-Alaska Electric cooperative proposed to electrify the pump stations of the pipeline south of the Yukon River and create a 138 kV “backbone system” that could support future load growth and generation opportunities, including potential geothermal power from the Wrangell Mountains. The G&T cooperative would operate on a non-profit basis, passing along all its costs and benefits to its members. “System wide scheduling of generation resources will be required...to achieve optimal costs,” concluded a 1972 economic analysis by consultants CH2M Hill. The study envisioned that 765 MW of generating capacity would be required to meet the needs of TAPS and regional utilities by the year 2000. The proposal called for the construction of a Palmer–Glenallen transmission line to connect Anchorage with the Yukon River–Valdez electrical system. Once again, Alaskans were looking at a large industrial megaproject to justify the creation of a Railbelt grid. Ultimately, the oil majors behind the TAPS project did not negotiate an agreement with the Trans-Alaska Electric cooperative, and the proposed G&T died a paper utility.

Independent of Alyeska and the Trans-Alaska Pipeline System, in 1972, federal and state planners considered the possibility of a high-voltage system to bring gas-fired electricity from the North Slope to Fairbanks and the Railbelt.¹³⁰ During the 1950s and 1960s, 600 kV and 700 kV transmission lines were constructed throughout North America (Hydro-Québec built the first 735 kV line in 1965), and utilities envisioned ever-higher voltage lines to keep up with the ever-growing load.¹³¹ The Alaska Power Administration (U.S. Department of Energy) followed up this study in 1982 with a proposal for an 8 GW high-voltage direct current (HVDC) transmission system but concluded the costs outweighed the benefits.¹³² While technically feasible, a high-voltage North Slope–South Central transmission line was projected to cost \$4.2 billion in 1982 (roughly \$13.3 billion in 2023 dollars). The oil crises of the 1970s stopped widespread electrification load growth and reduced the impetus for high-voltage transmission lines throughout North America. Around 2010, this idea was revived in the form of a 10 GW gas-fired power plant on the North Slope that would send power to Calgary and the North American electrical grid via a 2,300-mile 800 kV HVDC underground line. Project supporters claimed the HVDC system offered a viable alternative to a North Slope gas line.¹³³ While the idea of a transmission line from the North Slope continues to be a fixture of energy conversations in Alaska since the 1970s, it was uneconomic and infeasible in 1972 and remains so today.

The pipeline boom proved highly disruptive and challenging to Fairbanks. Golden Valley Electric Association stopped connecting new customers as electrical demand exceeded supply. Brownouts were common, and GVEA encouraged residents to buy individual backup generators. While utilities throughout the state grew with economic and population demands, GVEA grew at the fastest rate—in

¹³⁰ CH2M Hill, “Electric Generation and Transmission Intertie System for Interior and Southcentral Alaska” (1972).

¹³¹ Lings, “Overview of Transmission Lines above 700 kV.”

¹³² NANA Pacific, “Distributing Alaska’s Power: A Technical and Policy Review of Electric Transmission in Alaska,” Denali Commission (2008), 29.

¹³³ Alan Bailey, “Power from the Slope? Perhaps electricity production for L48 would be viable alternative to gas line,” *Petroleum News* 15, no. 49 (2010).

excess of 20% annually.¹³⁴ To fulfill demand, GVEA brought online a 120 MW oil-fired generation facility in the North Pole. This facility, constructed in 1976, sourced its petroleum directly from TAPS.¹³⁵ While the North Pole plant ended the recurrent brownouts in Fairbanks, ratepayers were saddled with higher rates from oil-fired generation amidst rising oil prices.

Despite the emphasis on electrification during these years, it is worth reiterating that historically, a fraction of Alaska’s energy generation has been converted into electricity. The real “gassing up” was the use of methane gas and oil for transportation, industry, and heat. Historically, electricity has constituted a minority of energy consumption in the Railbelt. In 1981, only 5.9% of Alaska’s energy use went toward electricity generation.¹³⁶ While beyond the bounds of this study, the federal government emphasized the opportunity to electrify heating and transportation during the oil crises if this load could be met with lower-cost generation resources like hydroelectric, coal, or geothermal.

Figure 15: Alaskan energy use, 1979. Source: Alaska Long Term Energy Plan, 1981.

¹³⁴ Institute for Social and Economic Research, “Alaska’s Electric Power Requirements: A Review and Projection” (University of Alaska, June 1977), 2.

¹³⁵ Impact Information Center, “Energy Costs, Consumption, and Impacts in Fairbanks” (1977).

¹³⁶ Neil Davis, “Alaskan Energy Use,” May 1981, <https://www.gi.alaska.edu/alaska-science-forum/alaskan-energy-use>, accessed December 13, 2024.

By the end of this period, the Railbelt faced an inflection point not unlike that which Chugach faced in the early 1960s. Hydroelectric power offered significant environmental and economic benefits but faced high capital and borrowing costs. Moreover, Alaskans remained divided on whether to construct large hydro facilities that might impact salmon fisheries or be vulnerable to seismic activity. In comparison, gas generation units offered less expensive upfront costs but higher operating costs. Due to financial constraints that prevented the state and utilities from pursuing larger hydroelectric generation facilities, the University of Alaska’s Institute for Social and Economic Research (ISER) concluded in 1976 that “the optimum strategy for the region might continue to involve the addition of new gas turbines for base load power, despite their relatively high operating costs and despite the uncertainty over whether gas will continue to be available for electrical utility use.”¹³⁷

Chugach’s continued reliance on more gas generation during a period of phenomenal load growth necessitated additional transmission. During the late 1970s and early 1980s, Chugach constructed the majority of its 138 kV and 230 kV transmission systems in Anchorage and the Matanuska-Susitna region. CEA also constructed the 115 kV line between Bernice Lake and Quartz Creek substation (near Kenai Lake) in the early 1970s to meet load growth on the Kenai Peninsula.¹³⁸ These additions created a new southcentral “backbone” system that grew beyond the existing 115 kV Eklutna and 69 kV hydro lines of the 1950s and early 1960s.

While Railbelt utilities experienced record load growth and buildout of transmission and generation, the fundamentals of system operation did not experience a similar step-change. Railbelt utilities still operated as integrated vertical utilities as they had since the 1940s. HEA and MEA continued to rely on Chugach for generation and signed a 30-year contract in 1984. Chugach acted as a single system operator for MEA, HEA, and the City of Seward. This provided significant economic efficiency and value. By sharing non-operating reserves, CEA, MEA, and HEA had to invest less in standby capacity to accommodate forced and scheduled generation outages. Similarly, by sharing spinning reserves, each utility saved by spending less on unloaded operating generation capacity.¹³⁹ Despite these benefits, the entire Railbelt remained disconnected and relatively balkanized. According to Chugach’s own retrospective evaluation in 2015, the business model of the Railbelt in the 1960s and 1970s was characterized by “relative inefficiency, low resilience and moderate or poor reliability.”¹⁴⁰ More generation and transmission had not revolutionized the Railbelt system.

Despite the state’s focus on investing in hydroelectricity in the late 1970s and early 1980s, these years should still be considered as part of the oil and gas boom because of the generation constructed in this period. To meet the surging electrical demand from the pipeline boom (Railbelt electricity growth averaged 9.6% between 1965 and 1984), utilities continued to bring online oil and gas generation well into the 1980s. As late as 1984, Chugach commissioned the 85 MW George M. Sullivan Unit 8. Between 1965 and 1972, the statewide use of oil and gas increased from 36% of all generation to 60%.¹⁴¹ Electricity prices declined in real terms between 1960 and 1972, mostly because of Anchorage’s switch

¹³⁷ Institute for Social and Economic Research, “Electric Power in Alaska, 1976-1995,” 1976, 1–10.

¹³⁸ CEA, Regulatory Informational Filing on USO/ Transco, 20.

¹³⁹ CEA, Regulatory Informational Filing on USO/ Transco, 19.

¹⁴⁰ CEA, Regulatory Informational Filing on USO/ Transco, 6.

¹⁴¹ U.S. Department of the Interior, *Alaska Power Survey, 1974* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1974).

to methane gas (Anchorage consumed more than half of the state’s electricity).¹⁴² Despite the unprecedented population and generation growth during this period, by the early 1980s, the dream of an interconnected Railbelt remained unrealized.

IV. Oil and Water: Building the Bradley Belt, 1985–2002

In 1985, the Alaska Power Authority energized the Alaska Intertie between Willow and Healy. This “long extension cord,” as some would come to call it, represented a milestone in connecting the Railbelt from Anchorage to Fairbanks that had been envisioned since the construction of the Alaska Railroad. Like most transmission buildouts in Alaska’s history, the Intertie was directly connected to new generation sources—the planned but canceled Susitna hydro project and the Bradley Lake facility. Power from Bradley Lake began flowing to Anchorage and Fairbanks in 1991. Although the construction of this important interconnection was decades in the making, it proved to be the easy part: efficiently operating and upgrading the Railbelt grid was a tremendous challenge that Alaskans are still trying to overcome.

This period witnessed contrasting developments: while the arguably most important generation (Bradley Lake) and transmission (Alaska Intertie) facilities came online during this period, these years overall constituted a historical lull for G&T development. Far more generation came online during the preceding period (1962–1984) and the following period (2003–present). The aftermath of extraordinary generation and transmission growth during the pipeline boom created false expectations amongst utilities and policymakers about future load growth. Despite a lull in the late 1980s and 1990s, this period witnessed a wide variety of schemes for new generation and transmission, most of which were never realized. Like Susitna, other crucial aspects of this project were either never realized or failed to properly operate. The Southern Intertie between Kenai and Anchorage was never built. The Healy 2 coal power plant, supported by federal and state funds, was constructed and first fired in 1998 but failed to achieve commercial viability.¹⁴³

Railbelt generation and transmission growth during this period was defined by the boom and bust of the state’s petroleum economy. Beginning in 1977 and accelerating in 1979, the state earned billions of dollars from the sale of Prudhoe Bay oil. The state faced what scholars have coined the “polar paradox,” where high oil costs lead to higher energy costs for Alaskan residents and businesses but bring increased revenues to the state.¹⁴⁴ Following the second oil crisis of 1979–1980 and the corresponding rapid rise in oil revenues for Alaska, the state found itself in a financial position to invest large amounts of money in energy projects. Under Governor Jay Hammond in 1979, the state articulated its first energy policy, which stressed investing oil wealth in renewable energy sources that would reduce long-term energy costs. This investment primarily came via building hydropower.¹⁴⁵ Yet, in 1985, the bottom fell out of the

¹⁴² Institute for Social and Economic Research, “Alaska’s Electric Power Requirements,” 5.

¹⁴³ While operating today (2025), the plant is still struggling to achieve commercial viability and has been slated for shutdown under GVEA’s 2022 Strategic Generation Plan.

¹⁴⁴ Amy Lovecraft, et al. “Alaska’s Changing Arctic: Energy Issues and Trends for the Alaska State Legislature and its citizens,” Center for Arctic Policy Studies, International Arctic Research Center (University of Alaska Fairbanks), 15.

¹⁴⁵ “State of Alaska Long Term Energy Plan: Executive Summary,” August 1981, <https://www.arlis.org/docs/vol1/Susitna/16/APA1639.pdf>, accessed December 22, 2024.

global oil market, and Alaska was forced to dramatically cut back its spending over the next two decades. The prime victim of these cuts was the Susitna hydroelectric complex.

The saga of Susitna is a long and winding tale that is largely beyond the scope of this study; nevertheless, its history has several important implications for the Railbelt's G&T history. The first state appropriation for Susitna occurred in 1978, with \$119 million spent between 1979 and 1984 on studies, administration, and the FERC application process. In 1984, the Alaska Legislature authorized the Watana Dam portion of Susitna at \$3.75 billion and, over the next two years, allocated an additional \$300 million to the project. Due to its geographical position and large generating capacity, Susitna required interconnection with Anchorage and Fairbanks, providing a golden opportunity to link the Railbelt. This spurred the approval of the Willow–Healy Intertie. “Without the Susitna project...the economics of, linking Fairbanks and Anchorage in the near future are doubtful,” ISER concluded in 1976.¹⁴⁶

In 1986, the bottom fell out of the global oil market, and the Alaska Power Authority discontinued its licensing application efforts, effectively canceling the project. In the same year, the Alaska Legislature created the Railbelt Energy Fund (which had \$281 million remaining in 1987) to pursue non-Susitna projects on the Railbelt.¹⁴⁷ The Railbelt Energy Fund funded the Bradley Lake project, the northern, central, and southern interties, and the Healy Clean Coal Project.

While Susitna attracted an outsized amount of controversy and attention, the construction of the Bradley Lake hydroelectric project was the prime generation accomplishment of this period. The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers began investigating Bradley Lake in the mid-1950s, and Congress authorized the project under the Federal Flood Control Act of 1962. However, just two years later, amid a buildout of cheap Cook Inlet gas generation, USACE announced they foresaw no customers for Bradley hydropower at 9–10 mills per kWh.¹⁴⁸ The state took up the Bradley Project in the 1970s and began funding feasibility and permitting studies in 1979. Construction commenced in the mid-1980s.

Bradley Lake ultimately cost around \$328 million (including major capital improvements in 2013), funded roughly half from direct state grants (\$163 million) and half from general obligation bonds (\$165 million). The 120 MW facility provided an average of 380,094 MWh per year—roughly 10% of Railbelt energy needs—between 1995 and 2013.¹⁴⁹ Bradley Lake was the most important addition of low-carbon electricity to the Railbelt since the Eklutna and Cooper Lake hydro projects of the 1950s and 1960s.

While a cornerstone development of this period, perhaps the real breakthrough and innovation of Bradley Lake lay in the project agreements between utilities. Alaska's main Railbelt utilities executed agreements for the sale, purchase, and transmission of Bradley Lake electricity. These agreements were essential, as other than Homer Electric Association (HEA), no other Railbelt utility was directly connected to Bradley Lake. Under these agreements, HEA was responsible for transmitting power from Bradley Junction to Soldotna, and Chugach was responsible for transmitting power to MEA and GVEA. Crucially, the Power Sales Agreement created a committee—now called the Bradley Project Management

¹⁴⁶ Institute for Social and Economic Research, “Alaska’s Electric Power Requirements.”

¹⁴⁷ History of the Railbelt Energy Fund, 1987.

¹⁴⁸ Whitehead, *Hydroelectric Power in Twentieth Century Alaska*, 98.

¹⁴⁹ Roger Withington, “A History of Major Energy Appropriations, Including the Railbelt Energy Fund,” Alaska Legislative Research Report, August 14, 2014, 5.

Committee (BPMC)—that was “responsible for the management, operation, maintenance, and improvement of the Project,” including the “scheduling, production, and dispatch of Bradley Lake energy.” House Bill 356, passed into law in 1988, exempted Bradley Lake from regulation by the Alaska Public Utilities Commission (succeeded by the Regulatory Commission of Alaska).¹⁵⁰ This non-regulated organization, the BPMC, would play a crucial role in contemporary Railbelt G&T developments.

A series of new transmission lines were constructed to transmit Bradley Lake hydropower. Under the Bradley Lake Capability Agreement, HEA agreed to construct two transmission lines from Bradley Junction.¹⁵¹ The first involved 115 kV lines and stretched from Bradley Junction to Soldotna. The second, constructed five years later in 1996, spanned 60 miles from Fritz Creek to Soldotna and also involved 115 kV lines.¹⁵² These lines, as well as the Alaska Intertie, were the biggest transmission additions of this period.

The economics of connecting Anchorage and Fairbanks were not a foregone conclusion. The main reason why a Railbelt Intertie had not been constructed before the 1980s was the challenging economics of the project. “The benefits of interconnection are limited to the distances in which generating cost savings (including savings on peaking and reserve capacity) exceed the fixed costs of additional transmission facilities plus line losses,” ISER concluded in 1976. The existing interconnections of the Anchorage Bowl, ISER researchers concluded, “just about define the foreseeable limits to cost savings from interconnection, unless construction of the Susitna project is undertaken.”¹⁵³ In the 1980s, Alaska’s Division of Energy came to similar conclusions, including the finding that extensive, long-distance intertie systems were unlikely to be economical for Alaska.¹⁵⁴ Fortunately for residents north of the Alaska Range, the State of Alaska constructed the Intertie before Susitna was canceled. Its realization provided the indispensable transmission of Bradley Lake hydropower to GVEA’s grid.

The chicken and egg problem of generation and transmission development, epitomized by Susitna and the Alaska Intertie, was a topic of frequent conversation and debate throughout the 1980s and 1990s. Neil Davis, a professor and Chairman of the Alaska Power Authority, recognized in his 1984 book *Energy/Alaska* that hydropower development was fundamentally constrained by the lack of transmission. Davis also noted that building a “general intertie network” would have benefits for non-fossil energy beyond hydroelectric, including “major wind and geothermal resources in southwestern and western Alaska.”¹⁵⁵ The economics of transmission typically only worked out when paired with a new generation project, but once transmission lines were built, they found economic uses beyond those first modeled.

The Anchorage–Fairbanks Intertie (now called the Alaska Intertie) was finally realized under the Railbelt Energy Fund. A 1981 study for the Alaska Power Authority found that an Anchorage–Fairbanks Intertie

¹⁵⁰ RCA v. MEA, CEA, GVEA, Muni of Anchorage, HEA, et al. Supreme Court of the State of Alaska, February 22, 2019.

¹⁵¹ RCA v. MEA, CEA, GVEA, Muni of Anchorage, HEA, et al.

¹⁵² NANA Pacific, “Distributing Alaska’s Power,” 15.

¹⁵³ Institute for Social and Economic Research, “Alaska’s Electric Power Requirements.”

¹⁵⁴ Scott Goldsmith, “Short (and Informal) Review of Alaska Rural Energy Policy, with Particular Reference to Alternative Technologies”, Denali Commission, May 24, 1999.

¹⁵⁵ Neil Davis, *Energy/Alaska* (Fairbanks: University of Alaska Press, 1988), 475–477.

would have significant benefits for the Railbelt, namely by replacing higher-cost oil-fired electricity in Fairbanks with lower-cost gas generation from the Cook Inlet. The report recommended that the new line be built to 345 kV for the forthcoming Susitna hydro project. Without Susitna, the recommended voltage was 138 kV, which the line has been operating at since coming online in 1985.¹⁵⁶ The intertie was built and operated by the Alaska Energy Authority (AEA) between Willow and Healy and had a maximum transfer capacity of 70 MW due to system constraints, not design limitations. The transmission line was 100% funded by state grant funds and ultimately cost \$124 million.¹⁵⁷ As part of the project, AEA installed voltage control devices at Teeland, Healy, and Gold Hill substations to integrate GVEA, MEA, and CEA systems.

The functional and organizational foundation of the Railbelt grid was the contract between the intertie's owner (AEA) and its users. To effectively operate, manage, and utilize the Alaska Intertie, in 1985, CEA, GVEA, FMUS, AEG&T (representing HEA and MEA), and the Alaska Power Authority (now AEA) signed the Alaska Intertie Agreement (AIA). The AIA established a formal reserve-sharing pool and rules for the allocation of spinning reserve amongst the pool. It also established rules between members for the scheduling and delivery of power. The AIA also contained important provisions regarding coordinated under-frequency load shed and some energy pricing and penalty agreements. A management committee set up under this agreement, the Intertie Operating Committee (IOC), soon adopted NERC operating guidelines, just as other large interconnections had done in the Lower 48.¹⁵⁸ This agreement was amended and upgraded in 1991, 2011, and 2014.

The benefits of the Alaska Intertie went beyond economics. As part of the construction of the line, the community of Cantwell was finally connected to GVEA and the Railbelt grid. Before the arrival of centralized electrical power, residents in Cantwell had to rely on private generators. In 1973, an 8-year-old boy died in a Cantwell "generator house" explosion—a not-infrequent hazard of decentralized fossil generation systems.¹⁵⁹ The arrival of the Alaska Intertie and centralized power meant improved energy security and safety for Alaskans.

With the completion of the Willow–Healy Intertie, the Railbelt became a weakly-connected transmission grid. No sooner had the intertie been energized than grid planners looked to upgrade its capacity from 70 MW to 100 MW.¹⁶⁰ Additional studies authorized by AEA and the Alaska Legislature recommended several redundant and upgraded lines to bolster resilience and transfer capacity, especially with Bradley Lake scheduled to come online around 1990. In 1987, AEA's Railbelt Intertie Reconnaissance Study recommended new Healy–Fairbanks (later called the Northern Intertie) and Douglas–Lake Lorraine 345 kV transmission lines. The 1991 Railbelt Intertie Feasibility Study recommended a 138 kV Northern Intertie and a Soldotna–Anchorage "Southern Intertie." A recurring issue in these studies was the poor cost/benefit ratio of constructing the Southern Intertie. Yet, the dream of additional transmission interconnecting Alaska flourished during these years.

¹⁵⁶ 1981 Gilbert/Commonwealth study, found in NANA Pacific, "Distributing Alaska's Power," 12.

¹⁵⁷ Alaska Intertie, AEA (2019).

¹⁵⁸ CEA, Regulatory Informational Filing on USO/ Transco, 21.

¹⁵⁹ "Boy Killed at Cantwell", *Sitka Daily Sentinel*, December 20th, 1973.

¹⁶⁰ Railbelt Intertie Reconnaissance Study, APA (1989), 1–2.

Railbelt planners were interested in connecting with Copper Valley, especially after Copper Valley connected hydroelectric resources (Solomon Gulch) in Valdez with a transmission line of over 100 miles to Glenallen. In 1989, AEA's Railbelt Intertie Reconnaissance Study recommended a transmission line following the Glenn Highway to Glenallen and another line following the Richardson to Delta Junction. A separate 1991 study estimated this latter line would cost \$92 million and not provide sufficient benefits to cover the expense.¹⁶¹ Additional studies throughout the 1990s and early 2000s focused on a 135-mile Sutton–Glenallen line operating at 138 kV.¹⁶² These dreams continued those articulated in the late 1960s with the proposed electrification of TAPS pump stations but likewise came to naught.

A major degradation in CEA's financial position in the 1980s—in large part due to the pipeline boom and the associated population and load growth—created new avenues for both Railbelt cooperation and disagreements. Chugach's financial position became “untenable” according to a utility retrospective, and CEA believed it might not be able to honor commitments to HEA and MEA. The Alaska Public Utilities Commission ordered an audit of Chugach's finances. The financial fallout meant that CEA had to sell two of its turbines on order from General Electric—one to ML&P (George M. Sullivan Unit 8) and one to the Alaska Electric Generation and Transmission Cooperative (AEG&T).¹⁶³ AEG&T was created by HEA and MEA at this time and contractually envisioned Chugach's ultimate participation. AEG&T purchased and ran Chugach's second General Electric turbine, which became the Soldotna 1 plant (later moved to Nikiski).

During these turbulent times, CEA renegotiated its wholesale power contract with MEA (under the auspices of AEG&T) in what became called the Tripartite Agreement.¹⁶⁴ While the opportunity to form a traditional G&T cooperative was ever-present during these years, it fell apart due to utility politics and the Great Alaska Recession of the mid-1980s. Beyond another failed G&T cooperative, the experience led to protracted litigation between CEA, MEA, and HEA.¹⁶⁵

Despite tense and often litigious relations between utilities, the 20 years between 1988 and 2008 witnessed more coordinated Railbelt G&T operations. Greater coordination had a direct bearing on new generation buildout. In 1988, after CEA entered into a non-firm energy agreement with GVEA and soon after integrated AEG&T's Soldotna Unit 1 into Chugach's generation fleet, CEA established a single economic dispatch for most of the Railbelt (ML&P and FMUS remained outside of this pool). CEA served

¹⁶¹ “Glenallen to Fairbanks Intertie: Preliminary Assessment,” Alaska Energy Authority (1991), in NANA Pacific, “Distributing Alaska's Power,” 16.

¹⁶² See the 1993 Alaska Legislature \$35 million appropriation; Power Engineers, “Screening Level Cost Estimate,” 1992; R.W. Beck and Associates, “Copper Valley Intertie”; “Copper Valley Intertie Plan,” Alaska Department of Community and Regional Affairs, Division of Energy, 1994; CH2M Hill Study, 1995; found in NANA Pacific, “Distributing Alaska's Power,” 16; Tim Ellis, “‘Road Belt’ Power Line Supporters: Trump's Infrastructure,” *KUAC*, January 3, 2018; “Roadbelt Intertie Reconnaissance Engineering Report,” Denali Commission, November 2020.

¹⁶³ AEG&T became the Alaska Electric and Energy Cooperative in 2001. Eventually, HEA became the sole owner of AEEC but preserved this G&T subsidiary.

¹⁶⁴ Chugach Electric Association, Matanuska Electric Association, and Alaska Electric Generation and Transmission Cooperative, Inc., “Second Amendment to Modified Agreement for the Sale and Purchase of Electric Power and Energy (Modified Tripartite Power Sales Agreement),” April 1989, <https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/878004/000119312513121758/d505014dex1063.htm>, accessed December 23, 2024.

¹⁶⁵ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 20.

GVEA's incremental loads and provided load-following for GVEA, and GVEA became a part of Chugach's system-wide economic dispatch.¹⁶⁶

At the same time, a CEA–GVEA agreement over Bradley Lake capacity further optimized Railbelt-wide economic dispatch. Beginning in 1994, Chugach used GVEA's share of Bradley Lake power to obviate starting up one of its GE Frame 7's for peaking. In exchange, GVEA received a lower cost for the power CEA sent up the intertie. In 1996, GVEA and FMUS signed a dispatch and pricing arrangement that allocated the FMUS load between GVEA/CEA non-firm power and spot market power provided by CEA and ML&P. GVEA's merger with FMUS in 1998 continued the historic consolidation of Railbelt utilities (going back to the 1950s), and part of the old FMUS load continued to be served by a CEA and ML&P spot market.¹⁶⁷

During the 1990s and 2000s, the Railbelt was effectively split into two operating areas. With input from MEA and HEA and working in concert with ML&P, Chugach provided economic dispatch and regional planning to the Railbelt south of the Alaska Range. GVEA, working in conjunction with FMUS until the 1998 merger, provided economic dispatch and regional planning to the Railbelt north of the Alaska Range. As discussed above, GVEA's loads were also integrated into Chugach's economic dispatch during these years.¹⁶⁸ Coal continued to dominate generation on the northern half of the Railbelt, although proposals for a Cook Inlet coal power plant were perennial.

Ever since GVEA constructed Healy 1 in 1967, Alaskan utilities had envisioned constructing a much larger mine-mouth coal plant in the area. In the late 1960s, GVEA proposed the construction of a 110 MW plant with three 138 kV transmission lines to Fairbanks by 1975.¹⁶⁹ In the late 1970s, GVEA and FMUS announced they were discussing a joint venture 150 MW facility. While utilities believed the plant would be economically feasible, they recognized there would be significant environmental hurdles surrounding air pollution due to the plant's proximity to Denali National Park (then called Mt. McKinley National Park).¹⁷⁰

A permanent feature of Railbelt generation during this period was the attempts by multiple private companies to construct a large coal generation facility. This was driven by two major factors: a national concern over limited methane gas supplies and expectations of significant load growth and retiring generations. According to Alaska Power Association data, load growth and retiring generation units signaled a potential power shortfall near the end of the decade (as much as 650 MW by 2000). Amongst many proposals, the Usibelli coal company envisioned a 200 MW coal plant at Emma Creek near Healy, and Diamond Alaska Coal Company and Voss International proposed a 160 MW coal generation facility called the Cook Inlet Power Project for South Central in 1986. The latter two companies claimed that "future prospects of availability and price [of gas] are uncertain."¹⁷¹ Following the energy crises, the

¹⁶⁶ Chugach Electric Association, "Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO," 22.

¹⁶⁷ Chugach Electric Association, "Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO," 22.

¹⁶⁸ Chugach Electric Association, "Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO," 22.

¹⁶⁹ U.S. Department of the Interior, *Alaska Power Survey, 1969*, 74.

¹⁷⁰ Impact Information Center, "Energy Costs, Consumption, and Impacts in Fairbanks."

¹⁷¹ Cook Inlet Power Plant Project, 1986.

United States constructed gigawatts of coal generation, but other than one experimental 50 MW plant, Alaska did not follow this national trend.

Healy 2 was realized under the Healy Clean Coal Project as an experimental generating station in the 1990s. The original plan envisioned a cogeneration plant (heat and power) that would dry the coal for export, but the economics did not support this plan, and the project moved forward as just a power plant. The facility was jointly funded by the U.S. Department of Energy (\$117.3 million), state appropriations (\$25 million), and a bond sale from the Alaska Industrial Development and Export Authority (\$85 million). GVEA planned on operating the facility. After a series of lawsuits in the early 1990s, the facility was constructed between 1995 and 1997, with testing completed in December 1999. While AIDEA claimed the new plant met its technical objectives, GVEA argued the plant did not meet its operational and safety requirements. The plant remained idle from 1999 to 2015.¹⁷²

In 1993, the state legislature appropriated \$90 million to realize the Northern and Southern Interties as part of the Railbelt Energy Fund.¹⁷³ GVEA began planning a second transmission line (as recommended by AEA in 1978) from Healy to Fairbanks—the Northern Intertie—as early as 1991, when the contours of the Healy 2 facility were coming into view. GVEA claimed the line would help bring the cheapest electrons up from the Healy 2 unit being constructed, as well as transmit more economic power from Anchorage. GVEA also cited demand increases from Fort Knox, which was expected to need a constant 35 MW of power for its operations.¹⁷⁴ GVEA began permitting the 230 kV line to augment the existing Fairbanks–Healy Intertie in 1994 and received Bureau of Land Management approval for the Rex–South route in 1999. The decision was challenged by residents concerned about environmental damage to the fens of Tanana Flats.¹⁷⁵ After overcoming significant local opposition and logistical construction challenges, GVEA energized the Northern Intertie in 2003. The \$65 million project reduced transmission losses and increased reliability and capacity-sharing benefits.¹⁷⁶

The construction of Healy 2 and the Northern Intertie aligned with GVEA’s aggressive pursuit of large industrial consumers in the 1990s and 2000s, notably users involved in gold mining operations, which required megawatts of load to run crushers and other industrial equipment. In 1996, GVEA began supplying Kinross’s Fort Knox mine northeast of Fairbanks with 35 MW after it constructed a 30-mile 138 kV transmission line. By 1997, the additional load from the mine reduced rates for GVEA member-owners by 7%.¹⁷⁷ GVEA continued this strategy throughout the 2000s, with significant implications for G&T in Interior Alaska. While GVEA no longer promoted “total electrification” for its residential customers, load growth via industrial mining promised similar positive impacts for the utility and the rates of its member-owners.

In the late 1980s and early 1990s, Railbelt grid planners also devoted significant attention to realizing the Southern Intertie from the Kenai Peninsula to Anchorage. The original 69 kV (later upgraded to 115

¹⁷² Ginny Fay, “A History of Alaska’s Megaprojects,” June 2003; for lawsuits, see *Alaska Federation v. Alaska Utilities*, Supreme Court of Alaska, August 1994.

¹⁷³ Statewide Energy Plan, 2003, 5.

¹⁷⁴ “Golden Valley Mulls New Line,” *Daily Sitka Sentinel*, August 1, 1996.

¹⁷⁵ Diana Campbell, “BLM To Void permits if Intertie Route Altered,” *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, January 17, 2001.

¹⁷⁶ NANA Pacific, “Distributing Alaska’s Power,” 14; Whittington, “A History of Major Energy Appropriations,” 6.

¹⁷⁷ Patricia Jones, “Gold Mine to help Golden Valley Cut Rates,” *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, October 16, 1995.

kV) Quartz Creek line constructed in 1960 had a maximum transfer capacity of 75 MW, was prone to avalanche damage, proved hard to repair, and was beginning to show its age. With Bradley Lake coming online, the Kenai had over 200 MW of generation capacity in the 1990s but could only move a fraction of that energy via the SQ line's weak link. In 1990, a NERC reliability assessment found that the existing single-line transmission interconnections "pose a significantly higher than traditional reliability risk for system-wide blackouts due to single contingency outages." NERC concluded that this single line was less reliable than the Lower 48 connections, and a second line was required under traditional reliability criteria.¹⁷⁸

In 1987, the Railbelt Reconnaissance Study recommended three routes for an additional 138 kV line to bring Kenai power to Anchorage. However, that study and subsequent ones showed that the project had a poor cost/benefit ratio and that the Southern Intertie did not justify its cost. A heated back-and-forth between utilities and consumer advocates ensued throughout the 1990s over the merits of the proposed line.¹⁷⁹ After the state withdrew \$28.5 million in support for the project, Homer Electric Association backed out, and the project stalled.¹⁸⁰ For the next 30 years, the project remained on the drawing board.

Upgrading the Alaska Intertie and building the Southern Intertie both suffered from a lack of load growth on the Railbelt. The fallout of the 1970s oil crises saw a turn away from the postwar electrification campaigns. Increased electrification might have justified the upgrading and construction of these lines. In the 21st century, with increasing generation capacity at Bradley Lake, forecasts of increased load with beneficial electrification, and the need to transfer variable renewable energy over longer distances, the realization of the Southern Intertie is much more likely. In 2023, the Department of Energy awarded the state of Alaska \$206.5 million in matching grants for energy infrastructure, including an HVDC submarine line that would finally realize a Southern Intertie.¹⁸¹

Slow growth and the beginning of a historic transition defined the 20 years between 1985 and 2002. On the generation front, four major facilities were added—one experimental coal plant in Interior Alaska, two gas generators in Anchorage, and the Railbelt's largest hydropower facility at Bradley Lake. A profusion of smaller diesel generators for the military and smaller communities constituted the bulk of the new generators added. Thanks to Bradley Lake and its hydro lines, the share of hydropower increased dramatically during these years. Despite important advancements, this period proved to be one of slow growth, especially compared to the buildout of the 2010s. The 1990s were marked by a significant lull—no Railbelt generation came online between 1992 and 1997.

This period of building the "Bradley Belt" showcased the possibilities and limits of Railbelt coordination. Chugach's economic dispatch and the grid planning by GVEA and CEA meant that electrons were economically sent between Bradley Lake, Anchorage, and Fairbanks on a regular basis. The dream of the Railbelt grid stretching from Homer to Delta Junction was finally achieved. Despite some movement

¹⁷⁸ NERC Reliability Assessment, March 1990, Found in Statewide Energy Plan, 2003, 5.

¹⁷⁹ Alan Mitchell, "Southern Intertie Benefits/Cost Studies," prepared January 19, 2003.

¹⁸⁰ Ginny Fay, "A History of Alaska's Megaprojects," *EcoSystems: Economic and Ecological Research*, June 2003, 16, https://www.akleg.gov/basis/get_documents.asp?session=32&docid=81382, accessed December 13, 2024.

¹⁸¹ "Alaska Delegation Welcomes \$206 Million DOE Grant Strengthening Alaska's Electrical Resilience," Office of Senator Lisa Murkowski, October 18, 2023.

toward greater Railbelt cooperation (CEA economic dispatch, the creation of AEG&T, and the joint operation of the Eklutna hydro project), efforts to reform the Railbelt generally stalled during this period. By the 1990s, deregulation of the electric utility industry swept across the United States and seemed poised to reshape Alaska’s utilities, but ultimately did not reform the Railbelt’s vertically integrated utilities.¹⁸² Railbelt utilities continued to operate in the standard certificated utility monopoly system, just as they had since their founding in the 1940s.

Even with State of Alaska grant funding and power pooling efforts, Railbelt utilities did not construct power plants together or develop inter-area projects. This was due to the fraught politics of wholesale power agreements (including capital credit allocation), the non-contractual status of ML&P in the southern region’s planning structure, and the lack of a clear method for recovery costs from shared G&T investments. The Railbelt still lacked an entity with the authority and perspective to achieve Railbelt-wide coordination.¹⁸³ Alaskans had been dreaming of electric unification since at least the 1920s, yet when finally connected in 1985 and provided with the ability to conduct highly efficient economic dispatch, Railbelt utilities could not overcome inherent limitations to create a truly unified grid that coordinated all generation and transmission. For 40 years, the Railbelt has been interconnected but has not served as an efficient electrical *system*.

V. Repowering the Railbelt, 2003–2024

The last 20 years of Railbelt G&T history have been amongst the most paradoxical. Given the aging generation, Railbelt utilities made a series of pivotal decisions concerning repowering their generator fleets. While concerns over climate change and the falling costs of renewable energy intensified during this period, generation buildout continued to be dominated by fossil fuels. Despite a methane gas crisis in the early 2010s, between 2012 and 2016, the Railbelt experienced an unprecedented \$1.5 billion buildout of gas generation. Railbelt utilities consolidated with the takeover of ML&P in 2020 and FMUS in 1998, yet experienced a historic divorce in 2014 with the discontinuity of the Chugach wholesale power agreement. During these years, several relatively small but formative non-hydro projects emerged on the Railbelt, namely Fire Island and Eva Creek wind, as well as 10 MW of utility-scale solar between 2018 and 2023. The rise of distributed generation—with 16 MW of net-metered distributed resources—added a new and promising source of decentralized production. Finally, after decades of infighting, Railbelt utilities were forced to come together via an Electric Reliability Organization (ERO) and a Regional Transmission Organization (RTO). It is still unclear whether this will produce the collaborative breakthrough that the Railbelt needs for the efficient production and distribution of electrons.

This period began with a transformative investment in energy storage when GVEA installed the world’s largest battery in 2003. Due to reliability issues with the 1967 Fairbanks–Healy Intertie, GVEA invested in a massive (for the time) 27 MW battery for 15 minutes, or 40 MW for a shorter period, to provide energy resilience. The battery immediately made a large difference for GVEA consumers, prevented 300,000 potential outages within the first few years of operation, and saved Interior Alaska millions of

¹⁸² “Murkowski, Public Utilities at Odds,” *Anchorage Daily News*, 1997; Karl R. Rabago, et al., “Study of Electric Utility Restructuring in Alaska, Report to The Alaska Public Utilities Commission and the Alaska State Legislature,” June 30, 1999, <https://rca.alaska.gov/RCAWeb/Documents/Electric/CH2Report.pdf>, accessed December 23, 2024.

¹⁸³ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 22.

dollars.¹⁸⁴ The maturation of grid-scale storage convinced CEA to follow suit in 2015 with a small battery and HEA in 2021 with a 46.5 MW Tesla Megapack battery—enough to power HEA’s entire grid under summer loads. Beginning with GVEA’s record-setting battery in 2003, these investments heralded the beginning of Alaska’s grid-scale battery revolution. In 2022, Alaska ranked 12th nationally for battery capacity and was the fifth fastest-growing market for energy storage in the country.¹⁸⁵

Another important set of developments occurred in Interior Alaska during these years: significant industrial load growth. Throughout the early 2000s, GVEA continued its campaign to electrify large mines and industrial users. In 2003, Alyeska Pipeline Service Company moved forward with a “Strategic Reconfiguration” of TAPS, which included electrifying Pump Station 9 at Delta Junction. GVEA connected the pump station to its grid with a 138 kV transmission line that same year. Then, in 2005, the Pogo Mine north of Delta Junction came online. Soon, GVEA had constructed a 50-mile 138 kV line to feed the heavily electrified underground facility, which required up to 14 MW at any given time. As early as 2012, GVEA envisioned a 100 MW line running to Livengood to support the proposed Tower Hills mine.¹⁸⁶ To supply these large mines, GVEA constructed the North Pole Expansion Plant in 2006, bringing online a 60 MW gas turbine powered by naphtha from TAPS. GVEA’s construction of the battery energy storage system and North Pole Expansion Plant met local needs but was not coordinated with other Railbelt utilities.

Efforts to coordinate the Railbelt grid are almost too numerous to enumerate. These efforts remain paramount, as Railbelt generation and transmission—including new construction, operation, and maintenance—could have been better coordinated between the four major Railbelt cooperatives. Prior sections of this paper discussed paper utilities, such as the Central Alaska Power Authority (CAPA) in the mid-1950s, Department of Defense efforts in the late 1950s, federal efforts focused on large dam construction in the 1950s and 1960s, and the Trans-Alaska Electric Cooperative in the early 1970s. Throughout the 1990s, Railbelt cooperation occurred through the Alaska Systems Coordinating Council (ASCC). Alaskan utilities formed the ASCC as a state-wide voluntary coordinating committee and an affiliate of the Western System Coordinating Council, the western region of NERC. ASCC comprised representatives from GVEA, AELP (Juneau), Kodiak, Alaska Power Administration (federal), and Copper Valley. ASCC, working with the Alaska Intertie Operating Committee (IOC), adopted IOC operating guides and created a corresponding planning guide. ASCC membership and standards were voluntary.¹⁸⁷

In the 1990s, the Regulatory Commission of Alaska, the Alaska Legislature, and Railbelt utilities considered a wide variety of measures to facilitate power pooling, competition, and utility restructuring. However, none of these efforts produced a consensus or outcome that significantly changed the status

¹⁸⁴ “Golden Valley Electric Association: Increased Technology Produces Cleaner Energy,” GVEA Company Profile, 2006.

¹⁸⁵ “Renewables on the Rise in Alaska,” *Environment America*, October 6, 2022, <https://environmentamerica.org/alaska/media-center/new-dashboard-finds-us-wind-solar-tripled-over-past-decade/>, accessed March 19, 2024.

¹⁸⁶ Jeff Richardson, “GVEA eyes possible expansion to Livengood,” *Fairbanks Daily News-Miner*, March 21, 2012.

¹⁸⁷ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 21.

quo.¹⁸⁸ In 2005, CEA, ML&P, and GVEA formed the Alaska Railbelt Energy Authority (AREA) to combine expertise, resources, and financing power. The goal was to ensure the lowest cost power via coordinated planning and action. Efforts continued between 2005 and 2008 to consider the joint acquisition and operation of Fire Island Wind, Healy 2, and even Bradley Lake.¹⁸⁹

Friction and non-cooperation between Railbelt utilities were prevalent during this period, which had a direct impact on G&T development. In the decade between 1996 and 2007, Railbelt utilities were involved in over 50 lawsuits, most with each other or the Regulatory Commission of Alaska.¹⁹⁰ A 2003 Statewide Energy Plan concluded, “Inter-utility relationships occasionally result in disputes, e.g. over wheeling charges, utility participation in upgrades, etc. These disputes tend to spill over into AEA’s renegotiation of agreements. The renegotiation of an AEA agreement provides an opportunity for one utility to apply leverage to another utility, with AEA stuck in the middle as the ‘go between.’” AEA reported that their attempts to upgrade the Alaska Intertie and extend a wheeling agreement were impacted by these inter-utility disputes.¹⁹¹ These sentiments foreshadowed a breakdown that had a historic impact on Railbelt generation and transmission.

A full accounting of utility relations is beyond the purview of this study, but the result of this feuding was a historic disaggregation—namely, two pivotal divorces in 2004 and 2006. In accordance with the Tripartite Agreement and the CEA–HEA power sales agreement, in 2004, HEA and MEA informed Chugach that they did not intend to renew their wholesale power agreement upon expiration in 2014. They planned to construct their own independent generation to meet their local loads. Even CEA recognized that the business structure of the past 30 years was “inflexible and outdated” and the Railbelt needed a new path forward. In 2015, Chugach explained, “That business structure was a byzantine set of agreements and contracts interwoven in a labyrinth of implicit and explicit quid pro quos developed over some 30 years.”¹⁹²

According to one account of this period, the termination of the CEA wholesale power agreements—one of the most pivotal actions in the history of the Railbelt grid—precipitated several regulatory, bilateral, and multilateral actions:

Regulatory efforts addressed accelerated depreciation of existing generation assets and tariffs for transmission usage. Bilateral efforts tried to find other vehicles for maintaining interregional economic dispatch, operations, and quasi-centralized planning. Individual and regional efforts at integrated resource planning sought to identify the optimal resource mix, moving forward.¹⁹³

In 2006, another crucial Railbelt agreement—the Alaska Intertie Agreement—ended. The Alaska Energy Authority terminated the agreement primarily due to shortfalls in capital repair funding and continued

¹⁸⁸ See Power Pooling/Central Dispatch Planning Study, dated October 1998; RCA docket U-97-140(7) dated March 13, 2002; Study of Electric Utility Restructuring in Alaska, June 30, 1999; and RCA docket R-97-10(8) dated September 28, 2001.

¹⁸⁹ ML&P, 2008 Utility Profile, 7; ML&P Utility Profile, 2006.

¹⁹⁰ Patricia Young, “Lawsuits Between Railbelt Utilities,” April 5, 2007.

¹⁹¹ Statewide Energy Plan, 2003.

¹⁹² Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 5.

¹⁹³ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 27.

problems getting utilities to unanimously agree (a requirement of the contract). While the contract remained in place until 2010 due to the four-year notice provision, the end of the agreement caused a cascade of impacts. With the end of the AIA, utilities were no longer beholden to Railbelt reliability rules and contractual spinning reserve requirements. HEA opted out of the Railbelt pool but remained physically interconnected.¹⁹⁴ While the AIA was renegotiated and reinstated in 2011, HEA never rejoined the agreement, and the Railbelt lost one of its most important forums to coordinate G&T development.

In the wake of these divorces, AEA contracted two important studies to analyze the costs and benefits of a Railbelt-wide operating authority and resource planning—the 2008 Railbelt Electric Grid Authority (REGA) and the 2010 Alaska Railbelt Integrated Resource Plan (RIPR). An additional AEA study in 2014 showed annual savings of \$100 million by eliminating the duplications and conflicts of multiple transmission operators. The first two studies recommended over \$900 million in Railbelt transmission improvements, with significant efficiency savings for Railbelt utilities and ratepayers. To achieve these results, the Railbelt needed a new business structure and more unified operations. The clear conclusion was system-wide economic dispatch and a non-discriminatory open access tariff. In 2010, the Greater Railbelt Energy and Transmission Company (GRETC) was proposed as an entity to make this happen. Quite simply, the Railbelt grid needed to coordinate as a single regional grid. The real question was how to achieve this structure. Two prime examples offered were the Electric Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT) and the American Transmission Company (ATC).

Despite the important research and conclusions of these studies, these efforts failed to unify the Railbelt. As one unnamed utility individual put it in 2008, “Quite frankly, we have studied the issues to death and only need to act. What is likely preventing implementation is the lack of leadership from management and decision making from utility boards on a course of action.”¹⁹⁵

An important effort to unify the Railbelt came in the early 2010s with the creation of a Railbelt-wide G&T cooperative called the Alaska Railbelt Cooperative Electric and Transmission Company (ARCTEC). The goal of this G&T was to create a single operator for the entire grid from Homer to Fairbanks and to provide open access for new forms of low-cost generation throughout the Railbelt. Although four Railbelt utilities were part of ARCTEC, the non-participation from ML&P and Homer Electric Association effectively killed the cooperative.¹⁹⁶ Once again, voluntary utility efforts failed to unify the Railbelt and bring major benefits to customers.

Rather than greater unification, Railbelt utilities built \$1.5 billion in uncoordinated new generation following the 2014 divorce. Between 2012 and 2016, Railbelt utilities CEA, HEA, and MEA brought online 660 MW of new generation—an unprecedented average of 132 MW per year. Never before had Railbelt utilities or the federal government built so much generation in such a short period of time. These plants included the 200 MW Southcentral Power Plant (CEA/ML&P), the 171 MW Eklutna Generating Station (MEA), 128 MW of additional turbines at the George M. Sullivan Plant 2A (CEA), and a new 50 MW combustion turbine in Soldotna (HEA). While some of this generation was needed to replace aging units, much of it would not have been built if the Railbelt had been unified. One CEA study estimated the

¹⁹⁴ Chugach Electric Association, “Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO,” 26.

¹⁹⁵ Black and Veatch, “Alaska Railbelt Electrical Grid Authority (REGA) Study: Final Report,” September 12, 2008, 4.

¹⁹⁶ Ellen Lockyer, “Railbelt Electric Companies May Undergo Changes,” *Alaska Public Media*, January 16, 2014.

overbuilt generation to be between \$200 and \$500 million. This disaggregation resulted in lower efficiency throughout the Railbelt. CEA estimated the lost efficiency of economic dispatch at nearly \$50 million per year in 2015.¹⁹⁷ On the other hand, according to an analysis by energy analyst and HEA Board Member Erin McKittrick, these newer generators consumed less methane gas (an average of 4.6 billion cubic feet (BCF) per year) and collectively saved 46.2 BCF of gas, 2.5 million metric tons of CO₂, and \$325 million between 2013 and 2022.¹⁹⁸

Despite these developments, not all opportunities for collaboration and efficiency were lost. Chugach and ML&P co-owned and co-managed the new \$359 million Southcentral Power Plant with a 70/30 ownership split. The plant's design focused on fuel efficiency, achieving a 25% improvement over Beluga.¹⁹⁹ Following the acquisition of ML&P in 2020, Chugach wholly owned this plant. Furthermore, Chugach, MP&P, and MEA planned a "loose power pool" that prioritized running the most efficient units for the Anchorage area, starting in 2017. Ultimately, this plan did not come to fruition; when Chugach purchased MP&P in 2020, the Regulatory Commission mandated a "tight power pool" beginning in 2022. These power pooling efforts saved Railbelt consumers tens of millions of dollars every year (in reduced natural gas consumption and maintenance costs), in addition to annual carbon reductions of roughly 100,000 tons.²⁰⁰ Power pooling and consolidation saved 6 BCF of methane gas, 335,000 metric tons of CO₂, and \$47 million between 2013 and 2022.²⁰¹

Concern over the Railbelt's historic divorce and unprecedented \$1.5 billion generation construction led the Alaska Legislature in 2014 to direct the Regulatory Commission of Alaska (RCA) to study the problem and suggest possible solutions. The legislature asked the RCA to provide a recommendation on "whether creating an independent system operator or similar structure in the Railbelt area is the best option for effective and efficient electrical transmission." As the RCA noted in its June 2015 recommendation to the legislature, "Concerns about the fragmented, balkanized and often contentious Railbelt utilities have been raised numerous times over the past 40 years. Several efforts have been made to reform and reorganize the Railbelt electrical system, but none have succeeded."²⁰²

The RCA offered several high-level conclusions and recommendations. It found that the existing Railbelt electrical transmission system was inefficient and required institutional reform. The RCA concluded that

¹⁹⁷ Chugach Electric Association, "Regulatory Implementation Filing on an Alaskan Railbelt USO," 11, 31.

¹⁹⁸ Erin McKittrick, "Power Plant upgrades and utility coordination have saved around \$370 million in the Central Railbelt in the last 10 years," *Alaska Energy Blog*, December 11, 2023, <https://www.alaskaenergy.org/p/power-plant-upgrades-and-utility>, accessed December 26, 2023.

¹⁹⁹ Justin Martino, "Southcentral Power Project: Efficiency in Central Anchorage," *Power Engineering*, 2014; Robert Peltier, "Top Plant: Southcentral Power Project, Anchorage, Alaska," *Power*, 2013.

²⁰⁰ Ashley Theron-Ord, "Alaskan Utilities Sign Power Pooling Agreement," *Smart Energy International*, 2017; "Operations Agreement for Power Pooling and Joint Dispatch: By and Between Chugach Electric Association, Inc. and Matanuska Electric Association, Inc.," July 15, 2020, https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/878004/000087800420000015/c004-20200716xex10_87.htm, accessed December 26, 2024.

²⁰¹ McKittrick, "Power Plant upgrades and utility coordination."

²⁰² RCA to Sen. Kevin Meyer and Rep. Mike Chenault, "Regulatory Commission of Alaska Recommendation to the Legislature," June 30, 2015, https://rca.alaska.gov/RCAWeb/Documents/RCA_Recommendation_to_Legislature.pdf, accessed December 29, 2024.

if the Railbelt electric grid were constructed from a blank slate today, “a single utility owning and operating all of the generation, transmission, and distribution assets would probably be the most efficient and effective system.” However, it also recognized that the creation of a large public or private utility serving the entire Railbelt was highly unlikely because of the state’s “serious financial constraints” and acquisition difficulties for an investor-owned utility. The RCA called for the creation of an independent electric transmission company to reliably and transparently operate the Railbelt grid. Furthermore, the Railbelt grid should utilize system-wide merit order dispatch. The RCA concluded that while “many past efforts to reform and rationalize the Railbelt electrical grid have failed,” utilities must be given the opportunity to come together voluntarily. If these efforts failed, the RCA concluded it would work with the Alaska Legislature and Administration to realize an independent Railbelt electric transmission company.²⁰³ This is exactly what happened, as five years (2014–2020) of voluntary efforts to establish a Railbelt electric transmission company, or TRANSCO, failed.²⁰⁴

The single most important effort to unify the Railbelt during this period came under the auspices of the Railbelt Reliability Council (RRC). First proposed by the principals of ARCTEC in 2017, the RRC evolved from a voluntary effort amongst utilities to become the Railbelt’s certificated Electric Reliability Organization. Amidst the failure to establish an effective TRANSCO, all six Railbelt utilities signed a Memorandum of Understanding in December 2019. Following up on the RCA’s 2015 recommendations, the Alaska Legislature passed Senate Bill 123 to create an effective ERO in 2020. In September 2022, the RCA certificated the RRC as the official ERO of the Railbelt. The RRC has the authority to create “open and non-discriminatory” interconnection and transmission standards, Railbelt-wide reliability standards, and planning future power generation via integrated resource plans.²⁰⁵ The RRC represents the culmination of decades of work by advocates for a more efficient, reliable, and low-carbon Railbelt grid.

In 2024, the Alaska Legislature passed another key piece of legislation aimed at stitching together the Railbelt—House Bill 307. The legislation established a state-funded Railbelt Transmission Organization to establish and administer a non-discriminatory open-access transmission and created a new way to fairly allocate transmission costs. Crucially, the legislation eliminated “pancaked tariffs” and “wheeling,” which had proven serious barriers to the development of Railbelt-wide renewable energy projects.²⁰⁶ While the ERO and RTO constitute the most important legislatively directed efforts to unify the dRailbelt, time will tell if these efforts will be effective in coordinating the efficient operation of Railbelt generation and transmission.

These legislative efforts to create a more unified Railbelt occurred in the wake of a pivotal decade for Railbelt generation and transmission. With soaring oil prices in the late 2000s and restructured oil takes, the State of Alaska had billions of dollars in surplus revenue in the early 2010s. Efforts to unite the

²⁰³ RCA to Meyer and Chenault, “Regulatory Commission of Alaska Recommendation to the Legislature.”

²⁰⁴ Danny Kreilkamp, “The Railbelt Reimagined: Navigating an Energy Landscape that Works for Alaska,” *Alaska Business Magazine*, September 2020.

²⁰⁵ Brian Kassof, “RCA Certificates Railbelt Reliability Council as Alaska’s First Electric Reliability Organization,” *Alaska Transparency Project*, November 30, 2022, <https://www.akenergytransparency.org/news/rca-certificates-railbelt-reliability-council-as-alaskas-first-electric-reliability-organization>, accessed December 29, 2024.

²⁰⁶ Yereth Rosen, “Alaska House Approves Bill Designed to Unify Railbelt Electric Transmission System,” *Alaska Beacon*, May 15, 2024, <https://alaskabeacon.com/2024/05/15/alaska-house-approves-bill-designed-to-unify-railbelt-electric-transmission-system/>, accessed December 31, 2024.

Railbelt and create a 230 kV backbone grid returned to an old historic playbook—build large-scale hydropower and upgrade transmission to move bulk power. Thus, the state brushed off its old 1980s plan for Susitna. Throughout the 2010s, the state spent hundreds of millions of dollars trying to revive Susitna. Like the 1980s, the Railbelt’s greatest success in the 2010s with hydroelectricity revolved around Bradley Lake. In 2011, the legislature appropriated \$6.5 million for work on the Battle Creek diversion. This project, completed in 2020, diverted water from Battle Creek to the Bradley Lake reservoir, thereby increasing the amount of power the turbines could produce throughout the year.²⁰⁷ This iterative investment approach may continue to pay dividends for the Railbelt in the 2030s if AEA and Railbelt utilities decide to pursue the Dixon Diversion project.

While the historic buildout of hundreds of megawatts of new gas generation dominated this period, several important non-hydro renewable energy projects signaled the growing Railbelt focus on “alternative energy” investments (in the parlance of the day). Independent power producer Alaska Environmental Power gradually brought online the first major Railbelt wind project—a 1.9 MW project with three turbines—at Delta Junction between 2008 and 2013. This was quickly followed by the two largest wind farms on the Railbelt, the 18 MW Fire Island project outside of Anchorage and the 24.6 MW Eva Creek project near Healy. JBER’s 11.5 MW landfill gas project in 2012 added renewable natural gas to the Railbelt grid for the first time and showcased the U.S. military’s increased investment in renewable energy.

While gas and renewables pair quite well in theory, this has largely not been the case on the Railbelt. GVEA, with more than half of installed Railbelt wind capacity, lacked direct access to gas to regulate these variable renewable resources. CEA could regulate Fire Island with gas but did not facilitate additional wind growth. Fire Island wind could have been sold to other utilities like GVEA, but “pancaking rates” imposed prohibitive transportation costs and killed an expansion of the project.

Perhaps most underappreciated during this period was the rise of distributed generation and storage. In the early 2010s, the RCA adopted net metering regulations, which enabled Alaskans to sell excess electricity back to the grid from solar, wind, and other renewable energy facilities. By the end of 2024, 16 MW of distributed generation (almost all solar) had been installed on the Railbelt. Between 2019 and 2023, an average of 400 new net metered installations were installed each year. Despite these impressive statistics, the low capacity factor for solar photovoltaics means that all of these installations only constituted .3% of total Railbelt retail sales.²⁰⁸

The widespread adoption of electric vehicles beginning in the 2010s not only added a significant new source of load but also a valuable new distributed storage asset. With roughly 1,500 battery electric vehicles on the Railbelt by 2024, the battery capacity of these consumer-owned vehicles is equivalent to a 5.4 MW (90 MWh) battery—the longest-duration battery on the Railbelt.²⁰⁹ Put another way, the

²⁰⁷ Withington, “A History of Major Railbelt Energy Appropriations,” 5.

²⁰⁸ Chris Pike, “2023 Alaska Railbelt Net Metering Update,” https://www.uaf.edu/acep/files/research/solar-tech/2023NetMeteringUpdate_Final.pdf

²⁰⁹ Assuming 100% participation in a vehicle-to-grid program, where the average EV can generate 3.6 kW and has a 60 kWh battery.

capacity of electric vehicles on the grid in 2024 is almost equivalent to the largest generator constructed during World War II (Fort Richardson) and could provide continuous power for nearly four days.

The modern story of coal—the rock that powered the Railbelt’s creation—has been one of mixed fortunes during this recent period. In 2016, the steam turbines at Clear Air Force Base stopped spinning. The U.S. Air Force shuttered the 22 MW coal plant—nationally one of its most expensive power sources—and replaced it with a mix of diesel generators for heat and backup power and electricity from GVEA. The closure of this coal plant marked the first coal plant shuttered and not replaced with coal in Interior Alaska. In the long view, its closure marked the beginning of the end for coal in Interior Alaska (the end of coal for southcentral began when the first gas turbine came online at Bernice Lake in 1962 and replaced nearly all Anchorage coal generation by the end of the decade). After protracted lawsuits with the Alaska Industrial Development and Export Authority (AIDEA) throughout the 2000s, GVEA agreed to purchase and run the experimental Healy 2. The plant required tens of millions of dollars to make it operational. High costs, continued maintenance issues, and low reliability caused GVEA to vote in 2022 to close the dysfunctional plant.

Despite its high carbon emissions and air pollution, coal still offered value and energy security for Interior Alaska. In 2020, the University of Alaska Fairbanks brought online a 17 MW combined heat and power coal plant to replace its aging Atkinson units 1 and 2 (built in 1964). This plant may well be the last coal plant built in the U.S.; nevertheless, its construction signaled the enduring importance of coal—both politically and as a natural resource—for Interior Alaska.

During the past 20 years, the hazards of climate change have become increasingly prevalent on the Railbelt. The Swan Lake Fire of 2019 destroyed parts of the aging SQ line, cutting off Bradley Lake and its cheap hydropower from Anchorage and Fairbanks. This disruption cost Railbelt ratepayers tens of millions of dollars, as they were forced to burn higher-priced fossil fuels instead of relying on cheap and low-carbon hydropower. Climate change increasingly threatens the very integrity of the Railbelt grid Alaskans have worked so hard to create since the 1950s. As the destruction of Puerto Rico’s grid from Hurricane Maria demonstrated (the largest blackout in U.S. history), a single natural disaster can destroy vital infrastructure that has taken a century to build.²¹⁰

In the context of energy security, it's not surprising that Alaskans continue to dream of a redundant 230 kV grid. Such a system is imperative not only to allow clean electrons to flow effortlessly across the Railbelt in a carbon-constrained world, but also to build resilience in an increasingly dangerous natural environment. Alaska’s Railbelt grid has historically produced significant amounts of carbon pollution; today, it is the single most important machine for Alaska to reduce its carbon emissions.

Conclusion: More Than Just Wires

For 120 years, Alaskans have utilized a diverse mix of natural resources, built a wide range of generation stations, and interconnected the relatively weak but expansive Railbelt grid—the largest U.S. grid outside of the Lower 48. Yet, Railbelt utilities have been unable to come together to forge unified G&T

²¹⁰ “The Longest Blackout in U.S. History: Hurricane Maria”, *U.S. Army Corps of Engineers* 154, September 2022. <https://www.usace.army.mil/About/History/Historical-Vignettes/Relief-and-Recovery/154-Hurricane-Maria/>.

operations that would enable the greatest long-term efficiencies and savings for Alaskans. The long history of paper G&T utilities, paper interties, and balkanized decision-making testifies to the struggles of Alaskans to unify the Railbelt grid. Despite setbacks, the Railbelt can also be seen in another light: a miraculous grid that might have only been interconnected because of state revenues from oil production. It can also be seen as a grid that remains robust because of continued state and federal investment.

For most of the Railbelt’s history, there has been insufficient economic justification for creating a redundant 230 kV backbone transmission system independent of a single large generator. The cost-saving opportunities of renewable energy paired with the social and environmental imperative of decarbonization change that equation. Thousands of smaller machines—rather than a few large machines—may justify a high-voltage Railbelt backbone in the future.²¹¹ An expanded backbone system will be able to move electrons from new variable renewable energy sources from Chatanika to Seldovia, just as Neil Davis envisioned with the expansion of hydro lines in the 1980s.²¹²

Historically, generation remained paramount, and transmission was often a secondary concern. In the mid-2020s, with historic levels of federal funding and the likely buildout of extensive variable renewable energy generation, transmission has taken on a new valence. A recent report from Princeton University’s REPEAT project demonstrated that up to 80% of projected carbon emissions reductions from the passage of the 2022 Inflation Reduction Act will be lost if the pace of transmission construction is not doubled from its historical average of the past two decades.²¹³ Accelerating the pace of transmission buildout is essential to unlocking carbon emissions reductions and the full benefits of existing and future clean energy developments. Yet, as the history of the Railbelt grid demonstrates, the buildout of transmission must have a corresponding investment and focus on how to efficiently coordinate, maintain, and move power. Just as it has in the past, transmission and resource pooling will be the key to unlocking Alaska’s most efficient and prosperous energy future.

Coordination of the Railbelt grid is the single most important issue for Railbelt G&T development moving forward. The history of Railbelt G&T demonstrates that there have always been intelligent, forward-thinking individuals trying to increase efficiency and reduce costs by linking the Railbelt both physically and organizationally. This history also demonstrates there have been countless attempts over the past 75 years by these individuals and their utilities to create larger and more efficient systems. Yet, good intentions and earnest efforts have been insufficient to overcome inertia and barriers to Railbelt unification.

The history of the Railbelt shows that Alaskans can build ample electrical generation and create an interconnected grid but have struggled to efficiently operate, maintain, and repower the Railbelt grid in a sustainable manner. The sixth cooperative principle—cooperation amongst cooperatives—has been insufficient to compel utility cooperation. Creating USOs, ISOs, TRANSCOs, and G&T cooperatives has also been stifled by intransigent single parties and the accumulated weight of past disputes. Under the

²¹¹ For recent studies which look at decarbonizing the Railbelt, including load growth and transmission, see Paul Denham et al. “Achieving 80% Renewable Portfolio in Alaska’s Railbelt: Cost Analysis”, *National Renewable Energy Laboratory*, March 2024; P. Cicilio et al., “Alaska’s Railbelt Electric System: Decarbonization Scenarios for 2050,” Alaska Center for Energy and Power, University of Alaska, Fairbanks, 2023. UAF/ACEP/TP-01-0003. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10520543

²¹² Neil Davis, *Energy/ Alaska*, 475-477.

²¹³ “Electricity Transmission is Key to Unlock the Full Potential of the Inflation Reduction Act,” Princeton University Zero Lab, September 2022. https://repeatproject.org/docs/REPEAT_IRA_Transmission_2022-09-22.pdf. Accessed Dec 14th, 2024

historic status quo of the past 75 years, unanimous approval between the four major Railbelt cooperatives, as well as the three municipal utilities (ML&P, FMUS, and City of Seward), has been required to create a unified grid. Not surprisingly, considering the high bar of unanimity, unification has not occurred.

While increasing economic efficiency and establishing tight power pools would reduce costs for cooperative members, the economic and political risks of extending themselves proved too much. In focusing on their own territories and generation, Railbelt electric cooperatives are also doing precisely what they were designed to do. In this sense, the G&T history of the Railbelt has been defined as a kind of Alaskan prisoner’s dilemma, where prioritizing individual utilities’ needs has resulted in a suboptimal system for everyone. Without an external entity to facilitate and compel the shared utilization of resources, Railbelt cooperatives have remained balkanized and provincial. The current Cook Inlet gas crisis—with its very real possibility of running short on gas for electrical generation in just two years (2027)—has accentuated the ongoing tensions and “a fair amount of complacency” amongst Railbelt Cooperatives.²¹⁴

Effective Railbelt cooperation most often occurred when state entities (legislature or AEA) provided capital for generation and transmission (Bradley Lake and Alaska Intertie). To operate these joint assets, Railbelt utilities had to find a way to work together. Effective unification has also occurred when regulatory agencies have compelled utility involvement, such as in the Anchorage tight power pool and the creation of AEG&T with Chugach’s financial distress. The creation of the ERO and RTO follows these historic patterns.

With aging generation and transmission, the Railbelt is at an inflection point and must make a series of consequential decisions over the next several years. Like other pivotal moments in Railbelt history, Alaska may be on the cusp of another “golden age.” The passage of the Infrastructure, Investment, and Jobs Act and Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) constitutes the largest-ever federal investment in the nation’s energy system.²¹⁵ While the impact of a new president on these federal appropriations remains unclear, the change in Alaska over the next decade may prove to be the largest in the history of Railbelt G&T.

²¹⁴ Nat Herz, “Regulators, Advocates warn of utility inaction as Alaska gas shortfall looms,” *The Northern Journal*, December 24th, 2024. <https://www.northernjournal.com/regulators-advocates-warn-of-utility-inaction-as-alaska-gas-shortfall-looms/>. Accessed January 1st, 2025.

²¹⁵ Mark Jaffe, “Inflation Reduction Act could unleash \$3 trillion in renewable energy investments”, *Energize Weekly*, August 23rd, 2023. <https://www.euci.com/inflation-reduction-act-could-unleash-3-trillion-in-renewable-energy-investments/>

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